

inDICES

Measuring the Impact of Digital Culture

Deliverable 2.3

Legal comparative analysis evaluation

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 870792.

The sole responsibility for the content of this publication lies with the authors. It does not necessarily represent the opinion of the European Union. Neither the EASME nor the European Commission is responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Community's Horizon 2020 Programme (H2020-DT-GOVERNANCE-13-2019) under grant agreement n° 870792.

D2.3 – Legal comparative analysis evaluation

Final version

30 of June 2021

Grant Agreement number:	870792
Project acronym:	inDICES
Project title:	Measuring the impact of Digital CulturE
Funding Scheme:	H2020-DT-GOVERNANCE-13-2019
Project co-ordinator name, Title and Organisation:	Simonetta Buttò, Director of the Central Institute for the Union Catalogue of the Italian Libraries (ICCU)
Tel:	+39 06 49210425
E-mail:	simonetta.butto@beniculturali.it
Project website address:	http://indices-culture.eu/

PI: **Professor Marie-Christine Janssens**

Authors: **Dr. Arina Gorbatyuk**

Sonsoles Pajares Rivas

Emircan Karabuga

Centre for IT and IP Law, KU Leuven

Contributing partners: **Ariadna Matas, Europeana**

Dr. Konrad Gliściński, Centrum Cyfrowe

Table of Contents

Table of Contents	3
1 Executive Summary	4
2 Introduction and Objectives	5
3 Obtaining licenses for cultural content	7
3.1 Core principles of copyright and related rights relevant to licensing cultural content	9
3.2 Basics of a license	10
3.2.1 Challenges of licensing cultural content	14
3.3 Licensing ‘in’ mechanisms used by CHIs	23
3.3.1 Individual licenses	24
3.3.2 Collective licenses	25
3.3.2.1 Extended collective licenses	29
3.3.3 Open licenses	31
3.4 Licensing ‘out’ mechanisms for CHIs	36
3.4.1 Granting licenses to end-users	39
3.4.1.1 Open licensing for licensing-out strategies of CHIs	39
3.4.1.2 CC licenses	42
3.4.2 Mechanisms facilitating the rights information to end-users	44
3.4.3 Alternative mechanisms for facilitating user’s information	45
3.5 Conclusion	49
4 References	51
5 Annex I. Summary of inDICEs second consultation workshop	57

1 Executive Summary

This Deliverable (D2.3) analyses licensing models that cultural heritage institutions (hereafter 'CHIs') can rely on to obtain the necessary rights from relevant copyright rightholders to digitize and display their collections online. Since CHIs are often not the rightholders of the shared works, they are required to obtain an authorization from rightholders (if the works are protected by copyright or related rights), unless they can rely on applicable exceptions or limitations.

The process of obtaining the necessary scope of rights remains burdensome, complex and costly for CHIs. The obligation to acquire the authorization, at times even on an individual basis, may negatively affect the daily operations of CHIs. In fact, many CHIs struggle to stay connected with their audience in the Digital Single Market (hereafter 'DSM'). To continue to be relevant and fulfil their core mission of promoting access to culture, they are encouraged to share their collections online. This need was especially evident during the COVID-19 pandemic. Whereas CHIs may have previously established a licensing agreement with the relevant rightholders and acquired the right to display the works 'offline', the underlying license may not cover potential re-uses, preventing CHIs from digitizing the works and sharing them online.

To shed more light on how CHIs can deal with the increasing demand of being present online and the related need to obtain the underlying rights, we provide an overview of the available licensing models. In particular, we start our analysis with providing a brief but comprehensive introduction to copyright licenses and specifically focus on challenges CHIs face when negotiating licenses with relevant rightholders (Section 3.2). In Section 3.3 we pay specific attention to various types of licensing models available to CHIs, including individual, collective and open licenses, such as Creative Commons (hereafter 'CC') licenses. Finally, we analyse licensing-out mechanisms that CHIs can use when sharing digital copies of the works in their collections with end-users (Section 3.4). We conclude by providing a list of recommendations and attention points addressed to CHIs in order to facilitate their licensing strategies.

2 Introduction and Objectives

WP2 of the inDICEs project aims at providing in-depth analyses of how the EU intellectual property rights (hereafter 'IPR') impact the process of digitisation as well as the access and re-use of digital cultural content. The specific attention is paid to the opportunities and challenges the EU legal framework brings to CHIs.

In our previous research¹ we have shown how the objective of providing wider access to cultural content has gained further importance with the development of new technologies. The entrance of new technologies has also significantly disrupted the traditional activities of cultural institutions. These technologies did not only facilitate the dissemination and mass-consumption of cultural content through the internet but also blurred the separation between users and authors (creators) of works. In fact, any internet user have nowadays accessible and often user friendly means to express their creativity and develop new works. These new works may quite frequently be based on pre-existing works produced by other persons. These preceding works may be shared by CHIs in their (online) collections.

CHIs are generally expected to make the cultural heritage works available and accessible to the society. However, possessing a tangible artistic or literary object does not entail the ownership of the underlying copyright or related rights. CHIs need to obtain specific authorization from rightholders of works, displayed in CHIs collections, in order to make use of them, unless they can rely on an exception or limitation.²

Prior to exhibiting the works of their collections online and, thus, making them available to the wider audiences, CHIs must digitize those works by creating their digital reproductions (which does not apply for digitally born content). These digital reproductions are often referred to as 'digital surrogates'. As a matter of fact, following the findings of our previous deliverables, copyright restrictions are seen as main barriers to providing digital access to CHIs collections and facilitate the re-use of digital cultural heritage. In particular, the need to obtain the necessary scope of rights from rightholders prior to engaging in the digitization process and making them available is one of the biggest obstacles CHIs face on their way to become active participants of the DSM.

To obtain the above-mentioned authorization, CHIs normally enter into licensing agreements with rightholders. These agreements are legal mechanisms through which a third party is granted permission to use the copyright protected work under defined terms. By conducting a license with rightholders, CHIs obtain a required authorization to make certain uses of licensed works. In managerial literature such an activity is referred to as 'licensing-in' strategy. Without obtaining this prior authorization, and if the conducted use does not fall within the

¹ See Deliverables D2.1 and 2.2 of the inDICEs project.

² Christina Angelopoulos and Lucie Guibault, *Open Content Licensing : From Theory to Practice*, vol 48419 (Amsterdam: Amsterdam University Press 2011) 18.

scope of relevant exceptions and limitations, CHIs may violate the rights of rightholders and, consequently, be held liable for copyright infringement. In Section 3.1, we revisit the core principles of copyright and related rights relevant to licensing cultural content. In Section 3.2, we elaborate upon clauses that such licenses could incorporate, as well as highlight particular problems that CHIs may encounter on the EU level when licensing cultural content. For instance, CHIs may face difficulties when attempting to ‘clear the rights’ in case authors of certain works cannot be reached or identified (so-called ‘orphan works’).

To avoid negotiating numerous licenses on an individual basis, collective licenses, governed by collective management organizations (hereafter ‘CMOs’) may come to rescue. Copyright or related rights holders can instruct CMOs to administer and license rights on their behalf. CMOs can then grant rights on behalf of multiple rightholders in a single license for a single payment to an interested party, e.g. a CHI, significantly expediting and simplifying the rights clearance process.³ In essence, CMOs act as intermediaries between rightholders and parties interested in obtaining access to the protected works. Section 3.3.2 is specifically dedicated to collective licenses, paying additional attention to the extended collective licensing systems and its proven benefits for the cultural heritage sector (Section 3.3.2.1).

We also pay specific attention to the application of open licensing systems for the cultural and creative sectors. Such licenses are of great use to all parties concerned, namely rightholders, CHIs and end-users. Open licenses are copyright licenses that grant permission to any interested party to (re-)use a work with a few or no restrictions.⁴ In essence, these licenses allow copyright works to be shared more efficiently and under standardized conditions (Section 3.3.3).⁵ CC licenses, being the most used types of open licenses, are reviewed in Section 3.4.1.2.

Section 3.4 centers on the so-called ‘licensing out’ strategies of CHIs. CHIs need to set up these licenses to share the works on their websites or other platforms with the end-users. CHIs should be aware of the licenses and rights statements that they can rely on to, first, clearly communicate to their users the legal status of a shared work (e.g. whether it is copyright protected or in public domain) and, second, signal under which conditions the shared works can be (re-)used. Providing accurate and clear information for their users is key if CHIs want to benefit from the opportunities offered by the DSM.

The analysis is followed by an annex that provides a brief overview of the inDICES second consultation workshop which was aimed at obtaining valuable insights from CHIs on their IP practices.

³ <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/licensing-bodies-and-collective-management-organisations>.

⁴ <https://opendefinition.org/guide/>

In the next deliverable we aim at developing a number of IP-related criteria that are key for CHIs in their digital transformation process. The IP-related criteria will be visualized in an interactive flowchart that is being developed within the project in alignment with the self-assessment tool (Work Package 3) and the inDICEs participatory platform. The mentioned set of criteria will be the basis for the next Deliverable 2.4. These factors will also be clustered into two main categories, namely enhancers and impellers of CHIs in the DSM and will also serve as a basis for the final evaluation report (Deliverable 2.5).

3 Obtaining licenses for cultural content

CHIs hold a high number of books, artworks, paintings, sculptures, furniture and other creations in their collections. CHIs preserve, study, promote and facilitate the use of these works.⁶ Providing society with access to their collections has always been essential to CHIs. The cultural heritage sector has in general been driven by this public interest mission. Yet, the manner in which users access cultural content nowadays has been considerably changed by the emergence of new technologies and the internet.

CHIs have to swiftly adapt to new modes of sharing their collections in the digital world if they still want to be ‘relevant in the 21st century’⁷ and engage with the audience in the digital world. The COVID-19 pandemic has also amplified the need of providing (online) access to their collections.⁸ During the pandemic, cultural institutions have been forced to close their doors for a significant amount of time or had to drastically reduce the number of visitors. To provide access to cultural content to general public during these uncertain times, CHIs had to rapidly switch to virtual exhibitions, by, for instance, displaying digitized copies of works in their collections through their websites. Some CHIs had to also establish systems that would allow their users to lend digital copies of written works from their collections. As stated above, all these initiatives were essential to make cultural content available to their users, which were deprived physical access to galleries or other cultural institutions due to the pandemic. In essence, users engaged greater than ever with digital cultural content and visited digital collections more often than ever before, which was achieved partially thanks to CHIs being highly proactive in making cultural content accessible online.⁹

Before sharing the works online, CHIs clearly had to convert tangible works into digital files. The digitization of works poses few problems for CHIs that normally are not the right owners

⁶ Rolf H Weber and Lennart Chrobak, ‘Legal Implications of Digital Heritagization’ [2016] RESET. Recherches en sciences sociales sur Internet 1 <<http://journals.openedition.org/reset/826>>.

⁷ Lucie Guibault and Jean-François Canat, ‘WIPO Study on Exceptions and Limitations in Museums’ 1.

⁸ Ekaterina Travkina, Pierluigi Sacco and Benedetta Morari, ‘Culture Shock: COVID-19 and the Cultural and Creative Sectors’ (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) 2020).

⁹ See the research produced by work package 1 of the inDICEs project.

of the works in their collections¹⁰. Greater problems arise in relation to the acts of making (digitized) works available to the public through the internet.

It is necessary to highlight that in order to license in-copyright works to users, one has to be the rightholder of the work.¹¹ Normally, museums, libraries or archives that may hold a tangible artwork will not own the exclusive rights on works of their collections, which may limit their capacity to license-out the works in the collections (or even prevent them from granting such licenses). Simply put, the possession of tangible cultural objects, such as a sculpture or a book, does not entail copyright ownership on these works. Thus, CHIs are not able to grant authorizations for uses of in-copyright works to third parties, which significantly restricts the activities of CHIs, unless they obtain an explicit authorization from the relevant rightholders or if CHIs or users could rely on an applicable exception or limitation for the acts that the authorization will be granted for.¹²

Consequently, CHIs must have an authorization of rightholders of works prior to any use. For instance, CHIs are not allowed to perform any act in relation to in-copyright works in their collections, unless they obtain the necessary scope of rights from rightholders, for instance, via a license. Such authorization is, however, not necessary if CHIs can rely on exceptions and limitations available for certain acts such as for acts of reproduction for preservation purposes (which includes the digitization of works).

The situation, nevertheless, differs for the works in the public domain. The works can be part of public domain either because their protection has expired or because they did not qualify for protection in the first place. In particular, CHIs are not required to obtain authorization to use public domain works. The only exception is the obligation prescribed by some jurisdictions to safeguard the moral rights related to works copyright protection for which has expired.

Some cultural content in the CHIs' collections may be or may have been protected by copyright or related rights and therefore, the preservation, dissemination, access and use of CHIs' cultural content require the 'clearance of rights'.¹³ As was mentioned above, such authorization can be obtained via various types of licenses, unless CHIs can rely on a relevant exception or limitation. In the following section we focus on available individual and collective licenses. We also draw special attention to the new types of licenses that have emerged in

¹⁰ The digitization of works for preservation purposes does not pose great difficulties nowadays due to the exception and limitations that exist in the EU *acquis communautaire*. Directive 2001/29/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 May 2001 on the harmonisation of certain aspects of copyright and related rights in the information society art.5.2(c) ; Directive (EU) 2019/790 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on copyright and related rights in the Digital Single Market and amending Directives 96/9/EC and 2001/29/EC 2019 art.6.

¹¹ It should be noted that certain licensees may also have a right to grant certain defines scope of rights, for instance, if the underlying license allows sub-licensing.

¹² Gill Hamilton and Fred Saunderson, *Open Licensing for Cultural Heritage* (London : Facet Publishing 2017) 50.

¹³ The clearance of rights could be understood as the process of obtaining authorizations from the rightholders for the uses of their works.

the last decade. In particular, we analyse open licensing models, CC licenses being the most popular ones. Whilst CC licenses only count as a small fraction of the licenses used for licensing cultural content, their popularity has been expended considerably during the last decade. They have in fact also been heavily promoted within the cultural heritage sector. In brief, CC licenses give rightholders an opportunity to grant the public permission (so-called ‘public licenses’) to use their copyright protected works under standardized terms.¹⁴ These licenses are not only useful for rightholders, but also for the users, as they clarify to the latter in an efficient manner under which exact (standard) conditions the content can be (re-)used.¹⁵

3.1 Core principles of copyright and related rights relevant to licensing cultural content

Before delving into detailed analysis of the available licensing schemes, it is important to first summarize the core principles and features of copyright and related rights relevant for licensing cultural content.

No registration. Copyright protection arises automatically. Contrary to other intellectual property rights (hereinafter ‘IPRs’), such as patents or trademarks, registration is not a prerequisite for obtaining protection.¹⁶ The lack of formalities and mandatory registries makes it harder to find authors and rightholders of works. Furthermore, the lack of transparency of copyright ownership makes it even more challenging for CHIs to obtain the necessary authorization to conduct their activities.

Territoriality of copyright. In our previous deliverables we explained that copyright, as well as other IPRs, is territorial in nature. The scope of exclusive rights is limited to the territory of the country that granted them.¹⁷ It must be noted that the development of the internet and new technologies confronted the principle of territoriality. Once certain content is shared online, it could potentially be accessed in any part of the world simultaneously, blurring the physical borders.¹⁸ Considering this new possibility to rapidly exchange copyright protected works worldwide, enforcing the underlying territorial rights is a challenging task, since they have to be enforced separately in each jurisdiction.¹⁹

Authorship and ownership of in-copyright works. When licensing cultural content CHIs must be aware of who the original owner of the work is. Further explanation on the issues of ownership and authorship is provided in Section 3.2.1. In brief, in *common law* countries such as the US or the UK, the original owner of the copyright can legally be a person different from

¹⁴ <https://creativecommons.org/about/cclicenses/>.

¹⁵ Angelopoulos and Guibault (n 2) 15.

¹⁶ The Berne Convention forbid any formal requirement of protection.

¹⁷ Peter Danowsky and others, *Copyright in a Borderless Online Environment* (Stockholm : Norstedts Juridik 2012) 23.

¹⁸ Danowsky and others (n 18) 35.

¹⁹ Danowsky and others (n 18) 23.

the author of the work, while in *civil law* countries, the original ownership of the copyright in the works is normally vested in the author of such work. This legal complexity affects CHIs since they often have to obtain the necessary scope of exploitation rights from the authors or other relevant rightholders – via a licensing agreement or through legal presumptions, e.g. for cinematographic works – in order to carry out their activities. Furthermore, the author could also transfer certain economic rights to other entities, which may create an additional complexity when tracking the rightholders. Not to mention that the works can also be co-authored.

3.2 Basics of a license

In this section we explain the basics of licensing. In particular, we elaborate upon the types of licenses available for CHIs, as well as their scope and main characteristics. Licensing agreements permit interested third parties, e.g. CHIs, to obtain the necessary authorization from rightholders to exploit certain protected works.²⁰ From a legal perspective, a license is an agreement through which a licensee (e.g. a CHI) leases certain rights to a copyright protected work from a licensor (e.g. a rightholder) under defined terms and conditions (see Table 1). While there is no global definition of a license within the *EU acquis communautaire*, we can find an explanation of the term ‘license’ in the Opinion of the Advocate General in the case *Falco Privatstiftung and Thomas Rabitsch v Gisela Weller-Lindhorst* where he describes it as ‘*a reciprocal contract, under which, in essence, the person granting the license confers on the licensee the right to use particular intellectual property rights and, in exchange, the licensee pays license fees to the licensor. By granting the license, the licensor authorizes the licensee to perform an activity which, in the absence of the license, would be an infringement of intellectual property rights*’²¹.

A license must be differentiated from an assignment agreement. The assignment of rights entails the complete or partial transfer of rights from an assignor to an assignee. A license, is, on the contrary, an authorization to temporarily legally perform certain specified acts, without the transfer of copyright.²²

Parties to a license agreement. At least two parties (a licensor and a licensee) are needed to enter into a licensing agreement. The rightholder of the exclusive rights on the work could be a licensor. Other authorized parties, however, could also act as licensors upon authorization of rightholders, Collective Management Organizations (hereafter ‘CMOs’) being a common example. The counterparty to a license agreement, the licensee, can be any natural or legal person interested in obtaining authorization to use a protected work under negotiated terms. In addition, some licensing agreements can also be concluded between online distributors -

²⁰ Hamilton and Saunderson (n 13) 49.

²¹ *Falco Privatstiftung and Thomas Rabitsch v Gisela Weller-Lindhorst* (C-533/07) EU:C:2009:257 [51].

²² JAL Sterling, *Sterling on World Copyright Law* (4th ed., London : Sweet & Maxwell 2015) 1208.

so-called intermediaries between rightholders and end-users (e.g. CHIs, stock images platforms) - and their users. For instance, CHIs could act as such intermediaries when they grant their users permission to (re-)use works in their collections. In order to grant such 'end-user' licenses, CHIs have to, however, first negotiate underlying license agreements with rightholders or they can rely on other licensing schemes, such as open licenses, unless there are applicable exceptions or limitations.

The principle of contractual freedom. Whereas we would like to avoid getting into detailed analysis of principles and norms of contract law, it is important to highlight one essential principle highly relevant for this deliverable, namely the principle of contractual freedom. In essence, contractual parties are free to determine the content and terms of their agreement, as long as they are in line with applicable laws.²³ This freedom, however, can be limited by mandatory rules prescribed in applicable laws. Parties are not allowed to contract out of mandatory rules, contrary to default rules, which could be contractually altered. For example, if a certain copyright exception or limitation is mandatory according to applicable copyright law, parties are not allowed to contractually agree to the contrary, such a clause or an agreement will not be valid. However, if a certain exception or limitation is default or optional, they may contract-out of it.

To be valid, the contract has to also be formed in accordance with the principles and norms established in applicable national contract laws.²⁴ Considering the described complexity, it is advised to engage a legal professional in the contract negotiation and drafting process, to ensure that the negotiated contract is valid and is in line with applicable laws.

Licensing clauses. The principle of contractual freedom explained above is the basic foundation for negotiating licensing clauses, or in other words the content of a licensing agreement. In Table 1 below we introduce and briefly describe core licensing clauses to provide CHIs with a basic overview of which aspects licensing agreements should generally cover. To insure that this table is of potential use to CHIs, the licensing clauses are described from the perspective of CHIs being licensees.

²³ E.g. Article 1102 of the French Civil Code. The subject of applicable laws, especially in relation to IPRs is a complicated subject, which will not be covered in detail in this deliverable. For more information please consult James Fawcett and Paul Torremans, *Intellectual Property and Private International Law* (Oxford University Press 2011), Toshiyuki Kono (ed), *Intellectual Property and Private International Law: Comparative Perspective* (Hart Publishing 2012).

²⁴ For more detailed overview please consult Jacques H. Herbots (ed), *Contracts . International Encyclopaedia of Laws* (The Hague: Kluwer Law International, 2011)

Clause	Description
Subject matter	Parties should explicitly specify which work or works are licensed in the agreement. In individual licenses (Section 3.3.1) between rightholders and CHIs it is quite common to specify one or several works. Numerous works are generally subject to collective licenses (Section 3.3.2), conducted between, for instance, CHIs and CMOs.
Rights granted	<p>Licensing agreements of cultural content should also specify the acts for which the rightholder permits works to be used. The main economic rights of authors have been harmonized at the EU level by the Infosoc Directive.²⁵ The right of reproduction of works and the right of communication to the public, including the right to make the work available to the public are the main economic rights. There are, nevertheless, other rights affecting CHIs' activities that need to be taken into account such as the right of distribution (for offline activities), the <i>sui-generis</i> right for databases or the lending right for the loans of written works²⁶. The right of adaptation, which is far from being harmonized at the EU²⁷, also plays an important role for the creation of derivative works and in the new modes of co-creation and re-use of cultural content.</p> <p>In essence, rightholders and CHIs have to specify in this clause which of those economic rights are granted via the negotiated license. CHIs are only allowed to exploit licensed works within the scope of granted rights.</p>
Type of license (exclusive/non-exclusive/sole)	<p>CHIs may choose from three main types of licenses:²⁸</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Exclusive licenses.</i> These licenses grant the licensee/ CHIs the right to use the licensed work on an exclusive basis. Even the rightholder himself is not permitted to exploit the work within the granted scope (e.g. territory, scope of granted rights), neither can he grant an equivalent license to any other interested party. It must be noted that open licenses (see Section 3.3.3) cannot, by nature, be exclusive. • <i>Sole-licenses.</i> Under this license the licensor/rightholder is not permitted to give a license to any other interested party under the same conditions. Nonetheless, he is still permitted to exploit the work himself.

²⁵ Infosoc Directive.

²⁶ See Deliverable 2.1 of the inDICEs project.

²⁷ See Deliverable 2.1 and 2.2 of the inDICEs project.

²⁸ The European IP Helpdesk, *Your Guide to IP and Contracts* (2019) European Commission 29.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Non-exclusive licenses.</i> This type of license allows the licensor to grant licenses to multiple licensees. It is worthy to mention that open licenses are always non-exclusive licenses due to their nature. <p>Exclusive and sole licenses generally entail higher remuneration than non-exclusive ones.</p>
Sub-licensing	<p>Parties should also establish whether a licensee, e.g. a CHI, is permitted to sub-license the rights granted to him by a licensor. Parties may agree that all rights granted under this license can be sub-licensed or only a certain limited and defined scope. They may also specify to whom such a sub-licensing agreement can be granted. This cause is of particular relevance to CHIs as they often act as ‘intermediaries’ between rightholders of the works held in their collections and end-users, e.g. visitors of (online) galleries.</p>
Territoriality	<p>Parties should also state for which territory the license is granted, to avoid any future misunderstandings. CHIs are, a priori, not allowed to exploit a licensed work outside the specified territory. Considering the cross-border nature (Section 3.2.1) of digital content shared online both the principle of territoriality, as well as territorial contractual limitations are challenged. As a side note, when the contract does not specify the territory of the licensing agreement, some national laws will limit the application to the specific territory where the contract is signed.²⁹</p>
Duration	<p>The license should also indicate its duration. The license can be given for a specific limited amount of time, e.g. three years, or for a longer period, e.g. the duration of the copyright protection. In case the duration of a license is limited, parties may consider including a clause which specifies under which conditions a license can be renewed.</p>
Remuneration	<p>Licensing agreements should also explicitly establish under which terms rightholders or other licensors will be remunerated. While parties are free to choose the amount and method of remuneration, some provisions on remuneration of rightholders can be found in national and European copyright laws. For instance, as a general principle, the Infosoc Directive addresses this matter in its Recital 10 which states that authors should receive an ‘appropriate reward’ for the use of their works. Further considerations are established in the Rental and Lending Directive³⁰ and in the new Copyright in the Digital Single Market</p>

²⁹ Carlo Scollo Lavizzari and René Viljoen, *Cross-Border Copyright Licensing: Law and Practice* (Cheltenham : Edward Elgar Publishing 2018) 61.

³⁰ Directive 2006/115/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2006 on rental right and lending right and on certain rights related to copyright in the field of intellectual property art.5 and 6.

	Directive (hereafter ‘CDSM Directive’) ³¹ . Often national laws also include some rules on authors’ remuneration. There are three main systems. First, some countries consider that remuneration must be made in accordance with revenues obtained from exploiting the work. Other countries grant authors a non-waivable right to obtain adequate remuneration for the use of a work. Finally, some countries instruct to provide an additional remuneration to authors when the contractually agreed upon remuneration is disproportionate to the revenues obtained from the exploitation of the work ³² .
Termination	In this clause the terms under which the license can be terminated are specified. For instance, a license can be terminated in case of a breach of a contractual obligation. Interestingly, the CDSM Directive includes certain rules allowing licensors/authors to revoke licenses in case of a lack of exploitation. ³³ Nevertheless, these provisions only apply to specific sectors such as the music or the publishing industry. Thus, the application of this provision to CHIs is limited. ³⁴
Applicable law	Parties should select the law applicable to the licensing agreement. The license will be governed by the selected applicable law. In case the applicable law is not specified, the rules of private international law will apply to cross-border relationships.
Dispute resolution	Parties should specify which dispute resolution mechanism is selected in case a conflict arises. They have a number of choices. First, parties may opt for litigation. In this case, the jurisdiction has to be specified, to ensure that they are aware in which country the dispute is to be litigated, to avoid the application of private international law rules. Second, instead of following the traditional litigation route, parties may favour alternative dispute resolution (ADR) mechanisms, such as mediation and/or arbitration. To ensure that the selection of the ADR institutions is efficient, parties may in advance specify which institution should facilitate the conflict resolution process.

Table 1: Licensing clauses: an overview from the perspective of CHIs as licensees

3.2.1 Challenges of licensing cultural content

In this section we elaborate upon certain challenges CHIs may face when ‘licensing-in’ (Section 3.3) or ‘licensing-out’ (Section 3.4) cultural content. This sub-section aims at providing an overview of core overarching legal considerations and challenges CHIs may face when establishing any type of licensing agreements. The more specific legal difficulties that

³¹ CDSM Directive art. 18.

³² Scollo Lavizzari and Viljoen (n 30) 65.

³³ CDSM Directive art.22.

³⁴ Scollo Lavizzari and Viljoen (n 30) 66.

are tailored to a particular type of a licensing scheme are elaborated upon in detail in the following sections.

1. **Ownership and authorship of in-copyright works challenges.** As was discussed in Section 3.2, CHIs have to obtain authorization from rightholders in order to use works in their collections (unless they can rely on exceptions or limitations). The lack of knowledge and/or transparency of ownership or authorship of certain in-copyright work may cause difficulties for interested parties (e.g. CHIs) to obtain such authorization. Not to mention the legal challenges that may arise in case of co-authorship or co-ownership of cultural content, especially in the EU as this area is not fully harmonized.³⁵

To explain the complexity, the concepts of authorship and ownership of works should also be further elaborated upon. As a general copyright principle, an author is considered to be an initial owner of the exclusive rights. Yet in the EU, this is not always the case since the concepts of authorship and ownership of copyright protected works are not harmonized at the EU level. Nonetheless, there have been several attempts to harmonize such concepts in the EU *acquis*, although they mainly relate to computer programs,³⁶ databases,³⁷ and audiovisual works.³⁸

In the EU, the initial authorship is determined by the so-called ‘creator principle’, according to which an author is normally a person that creates a work.³⁹ However, this principle may vary per jurisdiction and especially between *common law* and *civil law* ‘*droit d’auteur*’ countries. In jurisdictions that follow the ‘*droit d’auteur*’ concept an author of a work is generally considered to be a natural person that created that work.⁴⁰ Legal persons, such as companies or CHIs, have to, therefore, obtain the rights from natural persons (authors) that created the work⁴¹. The Enforcement Directive⁴² also presumes that the author of the work is the ‘person whose name appears on the work in the usual manner’⁴³. Nevertheless, in common law systems, while an author of literary and artistic

³⁵ Giulia Priora, ‘Copyright Law and the Promotion of Scientific Networks: Some Reflections on the Rules on Co-Authorship in the EU’ (2019) 9 Queen Mary Journal of Intellectual Property 217, 219 ff.

³⁶ See art. 2.1 of the Directive 2009/24/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 April 2009 on the legal protection of computer programs.

³⁷ See art.4 of the Directive 96/9/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 March 1996 on the legal protection of databases.

³⁸ See art.2.2 of the Rental and Lending Directive.

³⁹ Scollo Lavizzari and Viljoen (n 30) 71.

⁴⁰ There are, however, few exceptions when legal persons can be named as authors of works. Scollo Lavizzari and Viljoen (n 30) 71.

⁴¹ Marie-Christine Janssens and Benoit Michaux, ‘Intellectual Property Rights: Copyright and Trademark Issues’ in Laurent Garzaniti and others (eds), *Electronic Communications, Audiovisual Services and the Internet. EU Competition Law & Regulation*. (Sweet & Maxwell; London 2020) 396.

⁴² Directive 2004/48/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 April 2004 on the enforcement of intellectual property rights.

⁴³ See art.5 of the Directive 2004/48/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 April 2004 on the enforcement of intellectual property rights.

works is generally considered to be a person creating a work, for works related to creative industries, e.g. cinematographic works or broadcasts, a legal entity taking the responsibility and initiative for the creation of the work could be acknowledged as the author of the work.⁴⁴

The question of ownership remains mostly unharmonized at the EU level. Yet, some legal acts, e.g. the Rental and Lending Directive, provide particular presumptions for transfer of rights of audiovisual works. In addition, the CJEU confirmed the principle of the initial ownership of rights of the author of the work in its case law (e.g. in the *Luksan*⁴⁵ and *Reprobel*⁴⁶ cases in relation to film producers and publishers, respectively). However, Member States still have a high degree of maneuver when addressing the question of ownership according to their own legal systems.⁴⁷

2. **Contractual restrictions of exceptions and limitations.** It results from our previous research that CHIs often rely on exceptions and limitations to carry out the activities for which they have the mandate, such as preservation of works in their collections⁴⁸. Exceptions and limitations attempt to provide a balance between the interests of rightholders and the public interest or other fundamental rights, i.e. the freedom of expression, by restricting the exclusive rights of authors⁴⁹. Exceptions and limitations are statutory provisions and, depending on the legislator's choice, could sometimes be overridden by contracts. In particular, mandatory statutory exceptions and limitations cannot be contractually deviated from, contrary to the default ones.

At the EU level, and until the adoption of the CDSM Directive, there were few examples in the EU *acquis communautaire* that clearly express that such exceptions are mandatory and cannot be contractually overridden. They mainly relate to software⁵⁰ and the *sui-generis* rights for databases⁵¹. On the contrary, the Infosoc Directive which includes a broad list of optional exceptions remains silent on whether such exceptions, once introduced at national level, could be overridden by a contract. Yet its Article 9 states that the provisions of the Directive 'are without prejudice to the law of contract'. Recital 45 further highlights that 'the exceptions and limitations should not prevent the definition of contractual relations designed to ensure fair compensation for the rightholders'. Thus, one needs to carefully review the related national copyright laws to be certain that negotiated agreements are in line with applicable national mandatory rules that may limit the contractual freedom.

⁴⁴ Scollo Lavizzari and Viljoen (n 30) 71.

⁴⁵ *Martin Luksan v Petrus van der Let (C-277/10) EU:C:2012:65.*

⁴⁶ *Hewlett-Packard Belgium SPRL v Reprobel SCRL (C-572/13) EU:C:2015:750.*

⁴⁷ Scollo Lavizzari and Viljoen (n 30) 75.

⁴⁸ See Infosoc Directive art.5.2(c) ; See CDSM Directive art.6.

⁴⁹ Janssens and Michaux (n 42) 399.

⁵⁰ See The Software Directive art. 5, art.6 and art.8.

⁵¹ See art.5.2 and art.5.3 of the The Software Directive.

It should be noted that the CDSM Directive explicitly states that any contractual provision contrary to the Text and Data Mining exception for purposes of scientific research (where CHIs are beneficiaries), the exception for the uses of works for digital and cross-border teaching activities and the preservation exception will not be enforceable⁵².

Normally, exceptions and limitations and licenses co-exist in the daily work of cultural institutions. We have learnt from our consultation workshops⁵³ with CHIs (see Section 4) that it is complex for them to rely only on exceptions and limitations given their narrow and partial character. In consequence, CHIs often engage in licenses with CMOs given that licenses provide a higher degree of legal certainty against copyright infringement.⁵⁴

3. **Challenges on obtaining authorization in relation to particular types of works.** CHIs may also encounter difficulties in obtaining the authorization from rightholders when authors cannot be found or located. In this section we would like to draw attention to two particular types of works essential for CHIs, namely orphan works and out-of-commerce works (hereafter 'OOCWs').

Orphan works, or otherwise works whose authors cannot be known or located, hinder the use of such works by CHIs as it renders impossible for a CHI to enter into a licensing agreement with the author of the work when the cultural institution does not know or cannot find the relevant rightholder. While it is not possible to estimate the exact number of orphan works administered by CHIs, this issue was highlighted as very problematic for institutions willing to engage in mass-digitization and online dissemination of works⁵⁵. Due to the lack of transparency of authorship and ownership, it is extremely difficult for CHIs to clear the rights of these works by entering into a license with the rightholder to be able to legitimately exploit them. To solve this problem, the EU legislator adopted the Orphan Works Directive in 2012.⁵⁶ This Directive aimed at providing *a legally certain framework* to facilitate the digitisation and dissemination of orphan works in order to aid the large-scale digitization of collections or archives kept by various cultural heritage organisations.⁵⁷

⁵² See CDSM Directive art. 3 ff.

⁵³ See Section 4.1.4

⁵⁴ See Open Glam, 'Copyright Clearance and Labeling Works: A Primer: A Webinar with Annabelle Shaw, Melissa Levine and Victoria Stobo.' (August 2020) <<https://medium.com/open-glam/copyright-clearance-and-labeling-works-a-primer-ab40d0992582>>.

⁵⁵ See David R Hansen and others, 'Solving the Orphan Works Problem for the United States' (2013) 37 The Columbia Journal of Law & the Arts 55; Marie-Christine Janssens and Ran Tryggvadottir, 'Facilitating Access to Orphan and Out of Commerce Works to Make Europe's Cultural Resources Available to the Broader Public' [2014] SSRN Electronic Journal <<http://www.ssrn.com/abstract=2538097>>; Katharina de la Durantaye, 'Finding a Home for Orphans: Google Book Search and Orphan Works Law in the United States and Europe' (2011) 21 Fordham Intellectual Property, Media & Entertainment Law Journal 229.

⁵⁶ Commission Recommendation 2006/585/EC of 24 August 2006 on the digitisation and online accessibility of cultural material and digital preservation (2006) OJ L 236.

⁵⁷ Janssens and Tryggvadottir (n 56) 6.

D2.3 Public

In brief, this Directive⁵⁸ introduces an exception to the exclusive rights of reproduction and making available to the public ‘for the purposes of digitisation, making available, indexing, cataloguing, preservation or restoration’⁵⁹ of orphan works for the benefit of cultural institutions. Nevertheless, the Directive establishes certain prior requirements for a work to be considered as ‘orphan’. First, the most essential requirement is the need to perform a diligent search which is to be exercised by CHIs for each work individually to avoid copyright infringement⁶⁰. Second, CHIs need to register and record such searches. Once a work is declared as ‘orphan’, the Directive applies the ‘principle of mutual recognition’. It means that the work recognized as ‘orphan’ in one Member State obtains such status automatically without further conditions in the whole of the EU.⁶¹ However, in case a legitimate rightholder is ‘discovered’ later on, the full spectrum of rights vis-à-vis the work initially declared as ‘orphan’ can be reinstalled.⁶²

Whilst the orphan works problem can be seen as settled by the Directive, the reality shows that the Directive is far from providing a practical solution. The requirements provided in the Directive, and especially the requirement of conducting a diligent search, have been proven to be complex and burdensome for CHIs. It remains almost impossible to carry out the requested mass-digitization projects in a legally certain manner since they require substantial technical, financial and organisational efforts that often exceed the capabilities of individual organisations.⁶³ This difficulty can be exemplified by the few works that have been registered in the EUIPO orphan works database⁶⁴. In addition, the situation is further aggravated by two additional reasons. First, in order to make use of such exception, orphan works must be permanently in the CHIs’ collections. Second, not all works can be considered orphan. In particular, some types of works, such as stand-alone photographs, which correspond to the highest number of orphan works,⁶⁵ are left outside of the scope of the Directive. Thus, the use of these works can also be made with authorization of rightholders (even though they cannot be identified).

In essence, CHIs cannot rely on the exception for all orphan works in their collections, and even when they can rely on this exception, they need to fulfil costly and burdensome

⁵⁸ See Deliverable 2.1 of the inDICEs project on the OWD and Deliverable 2.2 for a comparative analysis of the OWD in particular Member States.

⁵⁹ Directive 2012/28/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 on certain permitted uses of orphan works (2012) OJ L299/5 art. 6.

⁶⁰ Orphan Works Directive art.3.

⁶¹ Orphan Works Directive art 4.

⁶² Orphan Works Directive art 5.

⁶³ Victoria Stobo and others, ‘Current Best Practices among Cultural Heritage Institutions When Dealing with Copyright Orphan Works and Analysis of Crowdsourcing Options’ (2018) <<http://diligentsearch.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/05/EnDOW-Report-3.pdf>>.

⁶⁴ See European Union Intellectual Property Office, ‘Orphan Works Database’ <<https://euipo.europa.eu/ohimportal/en/web/observatory/orphan-works-db>>.

⁶⁵ R Kerremans, ‘A Critical View on the European Draft Directive for Orphan Works’ (2012) 2 Queen Mary Journal of Intellectual Property 38.

D2.3 Public

requirements, including the risk of having to pay a fair compensation to the author in case the author of the work would reappear. Thus, CHIs often opt for entering into licensing agreements also for orphan works, e.g. through extended collective licensing (hereafter 'ECL') – see Section 3.3.2.1 – in those countries where it applies, instead of making use of the exception provided by the Directive. Nevertheless, the studies carried out by the EnDOW project show that most often CHIs cannot get licenses for such type of works. Yet, the new CDSM Directive⁶⁶ provided new rules regarding OOCWs and established a more generalized manner to make use of ECL, that may improve the possibilities for CHIs to use orphan works in the online environment.

Out-of-commerce works. An OOCW is a work which is 'not available to the public through customary channels of commerce, after a reasonable effort has been made to determine whether it is available to the public'.⁶⁷ OOCWs pose similar problems for CHIs as orphan works.

However unlike orphan works, the EU legislator did not provide any statutory provision to facilitate the use of OOCWs⁶⁸ until the adoption of the CDSM Directive. The CDSM Directive establishes a new regime for the uses of OOCWs by CHIs which has been positively received by the cultural sector⁶⁹ since it provides a clear legal framework addressing the legal and practical problems related to OOCWs. The Directive provides a dual regime which consists of a new licensing system and a mandatory exception.

The licensing system entitles CMOs to 'conclude a non-exclusive licence for non-commercial purposes with a cultural heritage institution for the reproduction, distribution, communication to the public or making available to the public of out-of-commerce works'⁷⁰. A substantially positive aspect of this system is that the license could include works of other rightholders that are not represented by CMOs (subject to certain conditions).⁷¹ Member States are allowed to choose the mechanism to permit CMOs to issue this kind of licenses. Since the CDSM Directive is (until this date) in the national implementation process, we will need to wait to assess how these new developments will be put into practice.

In a second phase, and only in case there is no CMO that complies with the conditions set in the Directive to issue the OOCWs' licenses, the so-called 'fall-back exception' could apply. This possibility ensures that CHIs will be able to use of the OOCWs since this

⁶⁶ See Deliverable 2.1 of the inDICEs project.

⁶⁷ CDSM Directive art.8(5).

⁶⁸ There was a prior initiative with the European Commission, Memorandum of Understanding: Key Principles on the Digitisation and Making Available of Out-of-Commerce Works (2011).

⁶⁹ Paul Keller, 'Explainer: What Will the DSM Directive Change for Cultural Heritage Institutions?' [2019] Europeana Foundation 9.

⁷⁰ CDSM Directive art 8(1).

⁷¹ CDSM Directive art 8(1).

D2.3 Public

exception allows CHIs 'to make available, for non-commercial purposes, out-of-commerce works or other subject matter that are permanently in their collections'. The fall-back exception can be exercised under two conditions: (i) the identification of the author or rightholder was unsuccessful and (ii) the works at stake are forbidden to be made available under commercial websites.

A very important element of this system is the cross-border aspect of this new regime since the Directive aims at helping CHIs promote their collections as widely as possible⁷². Both the new licensing system and the fall-back exception permits cross-border uses. Further, to safeguard the interests of the rightholders, the Directive includes an opt out mechanism.

4. **Moral rights.** We observed in our previous research particular challenges that moral rights pose in the digital environment⁷³ as digital content is much easier to manipulate and alter than works in a tangible realm. The online presence of digital works does not only entail challenges for the protection of the moral rights of authors but also for the licensing of such works across borders.

These challenges occur mainly due to two factors. First, moral rights are far from being harmonized in the EU, as explained in our previous research. There are not only multiple divergences in the types of rights in national jurisdictions but also on the duration of moral rights. Unfortunately, no harmonization at the EU level is envisioned in the foreseeable future. Second, moral rights are independent from economic rights and are inalienable, which means that the author cannot deprive himself of his moral rights through a contract even if the author would want to do so.⁷⁴ Nevertheless, moral rights can be waived in certain jurisdictions and under certain conditions.⁷⁵

It is essential that CHIs take into account the existence of moral rights when licensing cultural content. The fact that moral rights are both independent from economic rights and inalienable means that they will still prevail even when economic rights are transferred or licensed. This means that CHIs will need to pay attention to moral rights even when they have obtained consent from rightholders to carry out specific activities in relation to a licensed work. For instance, this situation can entail challenges in relation to the moral right of integrity when displaying works online, e.g. through virtual

⁷² Christophe Geiger, Giancarlo Frosio and Oleksandr Bulayenko, 'Facilitating Wider Access to Europe's Cultural Heritage in the Digital Environment: Opinion of the CEIPI on the European Commission's Copyright Reform Proposal, with a Focus on Access to Out-of-Commerce Works' (Social Science Research Network 2018) SSRN Scholarly Paper ID 3287734 13 <<https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=3287734>>.

⁷³ See Deliverable 2.1 of the inDICEs project for an overview and Deliverable 2.2. for a comparative analysis.

⁷⁴ Mira T Sundara Rajan, *Moral Rights: Principles, Practice and New Technology* (Oxford University Press 2011) 15 <<https://www.oxfordscholarship.com/10.1093/acprof:osobl/9780195390315.001.0001/acprof-9780195390315>>.

⁷⁵ Janssens and Michaux (n 42) 397.

exhibitions.⁷⁶ Further, in case the author has waived his moral rights in a particular jurisdiction (where it is allowed), it may not be valid in other jurisdictions.⁷⁷

In addition, the differences in the term of protection of moral rights within the Member States also means that when moral rights may have expired in a certain jurisdiction, they may remain in another jurisdiction. This is particularly problematic for the uses of works in the public domain, especially in relation to the right of integrity and the right of disclosure⁷⁸. In principle, the right of attribution of authors should pose less problems for CHIs since one of the CHI's public mission is to increase the knowledge of cultural content, including spreading the information of a work, i.e. the author(s) name. However, a problematic situation may arise when users utilize the works shared with them by CHIs to create new works without attributing the utilized works to their authors.⁷⁹

5. **Technical protection measures (hereafter 'TPMs')**. TPMs were introduced in the EU *acquis* through the Infosoc Directive⁸⁰ and are defined as 'any technology, device or component' that is designed to prevent or restrict acts in respect to in-copyright works that are not authorized by rightholders. Since the Infosoc regime for TPMs has been assessed in detail in our previous research,⁸¹ we will focus in this part only on the relationship between TPMs and licenses.

There is a broad variety of TPMs that can be used for rightholders to 'control' or restrict uses of their works without their consent. The most common ones revolve around encryption techniques or watermarks for works or even technological measures in the form of access controls such as 'codes' to access a certain work or to block the download of a work.⁸² TPMs could also take the form of electronic rights management systems (RMI) which consists of all information provided by rightholders that identifies certain characteristics of the work, such as authorship, ownership or terms and conditions under which works can be (re-)used.⁸³

⁷⁶ Rajan (n 75) 481.

⁷⁷ Danowsky and others (n 18) 41.

⁷⁸ Severine Dusollier, 'Scoping Study on Copyright and Related Rights and the Public Domain' (Social Science Research Network 2011) SSRN Scholarly Paper ID 2135208 36 <<https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=2135208>> accessed 23 March 2020.

⁷⁹ Dusollier (n 79) 36.

⁸⁰ Infosoc Directive art.6 and art.7.

⁸¹ See Deliverable 2.1 of the inDICEs project.

⁸² Lionel Bently and Brad Sherman, *Intellectual Property Law* (4th ed., Oxford : Oxford university press 2014) 318.

⁸³ Lucie Guibault, 'Evaluating Directive 2001/29/EC in the Light of the Digital Public Domain' in Melanie Dulong de Rosnay and Juan Carlos De Martin (eds), *The Digital Public Domain*, vol 2 (1st edn, Open Book Publishers 2012).

D2.3 Public

While the use of TPMs may restrict the circulation of cultural content in the digital environment,⁸⁴ this mechanism can also be used by rightholders in combination with a license to specify terms and conditions under which the work at stake can be (re-)used. This combination allows rightholders, on the one hand, to monitor the (re-)uses of their works, and, on the other hand, to stimulate its circulation.⁸⁵ To monitor the (re-)use more effectively, rightholders could install TPMs before sharing the work with others. In particular, to ensure that this ‘tracking mechanism’ is in place, copyright owners could explicitly contractually oblige CHIs, e.g. libraries, to install TPMs to prevent unauthorized uses made by the end-users. For instance, when relying on TPMs, one could confine the geographical scope of a license. It could also be used to limit the number of devices on which one could access the works, as well as set the limit on the number of copies of works users are permitted to make.⁸⁶

It has to be stressed, however, that some organizations such as Creative Commons have strongly advocated against the use of digital rights management (hereafter ‘DRM’) – including both TPMs and RMI systems- in the online environment since those technical means could restrict the circulation of digital content that is allowed to be shared without or with a few restricts or is not IP protected.⁸⁷ In other words, DRM systems may ‘overprotect’ digital content and the rights of rightholders. For example, DRM systems may not take into consideration the uses permitted under exceptions and limitations or by CC licenses (explained in Section 3.4.1.2).

6. **Particular attention to the EU cross-border licensing of rights** The feature of ‘territoriality’ poses problems when licensing digital content. Despite the lack of legal provisions within the EU *acquis communautaire*, the matter of cross-border licensing has already been at the core of the EU policy and law makers’ concerns for decades.

Partial solutions are, however, found in specific EU sectorial copyright laws, i.e. in the music sector⁸⁸ or cross-border transmissions via satellite.⁸⁹ The European Commission has addressed these matters in several communications such as the *Communication on*

⁸⁴ See Martin Senftleben, ‘Institutionalized Algorithmic Enforcement – The Pros and Cons of the EU Approach to UGC Platform Liability’ (Social Science Research Network 2020) SSRN Scholarly Paper ID 3565175 <<https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=3565175>> accessed 24 April 2020; Mark Jordan, *Putting Content Online: A Practical Guide for Libraries* (Oxford : Chandos, 2006).

⁸⁵ Danowsky and others (n 18) 119.

⁸⁶ Scollo Lavizzari and Viljoen (n 30) 67.

⁸⁷ Brigitte Vézina, ‘Creative Commons. We’re Against Digital Rights Management. Here’s Why.’ (4 December 2020) <<https://creativecommons.org/2020/12/04/were-against-digital-rights-management-heres-why/>>.

⁸⁸ Directive 2014/26/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 February 2014 on collective management of copyright and related rights and multi-territorial licensing of rights in musical works for online use in the internal market.

⁸⁹ Council Directive 93/83/EEC of 27 September 1993 on the coordination of certain rules concerning copyright and rights related to copyright applicable to satellite broadcasting and cable retransmission.

copyright in the knowledge economy in 2009⁹⁰ and the *Communication on an intellectual property strategy in the single market*⁹¹ in 2011. Cross-border licensing matters have also been addressed within the Orphan Works Directive,⁹² in the *Memorandum of understanding for out-of-commerce works*,⁹³ and in the new CDSM Directive.⁹⁴ Despite these attempts, cross-border licensing remains mostly unharmonized in the EU level. Finding a suitable solution is, however, essential to facilitate the process of obtaining access to content within the EU.

The choice of applicable law and jurisdiction is another problematic aspect. At the EU level, the importance guidance in determining the applicable law and jurisdiction are provided in the two EU regulations, namely Rome I⁹⁵ and Brussels Regulation.⁹⁶ Rome II⁹⁷ is dedicated to the law applicable to non-contractual obligations. In general, it is recommended to determine the law and jurisdiction applicable to the licensing agreement by including a provision in the agreement itself (see Table 1), as otherwise, the jurisdiction and laws that apply to the agreement will be determined by the above-mentioned instruments. As was explained above, when in conflict, parties can also opt to resolve their disputes via ADR mechanisms,⁹⁸ the use of which is also further encouraged by the CMR Directive⁹⁹ and the new CDSM Directive.¹⁰⁰

3.3 Licensing ‘in’ mechanisms used by CHIs

The online environment changed the way in which the audience interacts with cultural since the internet provides users the possibility to access, share and create digital works much easier and faster than in the offline environment. At present, emerging technologies and the internet blurred the relationship between the author and the users since the manner in which users connect with the cultural content has also considerably changed in comparison to the

⁹⁰ Communication from the European Commission on copyright in the knowledge economy COM(2009) 532 final 2019.

⁹¹ Communication from the European Commission ‘A Single Market for Intellectual Property Rights Boosting creativity and innovation to provide economic growth, high quality jobs and first class products and services in Europe’ COM(2011) 287 final 2011.

⁹² Orphan Works Directive.

⁹³ European Commission, *Memorandum of Understanding: Key Principles on the Digitisation and Making Available of Out-of-Commerce Works* (2011).

⁹⁴ See for instance the provisions on out-of-commerce works in the CDSM Directive art.8 ff.

⁹⁵ Regulation (EC) No 593/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 June 2008 on the law applicable to contractual obligations (Rome I).

⁹⁶ Regulation (EU) No 1215/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2012 on jurisdiction and the recognition and enforcement of judgments in civil and commercial matters.

⁹⁷ Regulation (EC) No 864/2007 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 July 2007 on the law applicable to non-contractual obligations (Rome II).

⁹⁸ Scollo Lavizzari and Viljoen (n 30) 89.

⁹⁹ See art.34 and 35 of the The CRM Directive.

¹⁰⁰ CDSM Directive art.21.

previous modes of cultural consumption.¹⁰¹ Whilst the main value of copyrighted content was created by the ‘scarcity’ of a particular content in the traditional relationship between in-copyright works and users, the value of contents are determined by the ‘number of connections between works and users who value them the most’ on the internet.¹⁰² This is the reason why, according to Gervais, social networks play such a vital role in the dissemination of content. Nevertheless, this situation has created important challenges for rightholders and for cultural institutions since it is no longer possible to dictate what users do with third parties’ works.

It is in this scenario where a clear licensing system and labelling of works is more important than ever. Licensing is key for value creation and for the protection of the exclusive rights of the authors. Licensing contracts permit both rightholders and users to determine the permitted uses of a work and the remuneration for such uses. For internet uses, the collective management of rights also plays an important role in this equation and CMOs viewed as essential actors for achieving an efficient copyright system in the global digital environment which (at least) solve or reduce the transactions cost issues.¹⁰³

In the following sections we will provide an overview of both individual and collective licensing systems with a special attention to open licenses (see Figure 1).

3.3.1 Individual licenses

Licensing of cultural content is approached in mainly two ways: individual (explained in this section) and collective licensing (in Section 3.3.2). To obtain an individual license, potential licensees generally negotiate it directly with the rightholder, who acts as the licensor.

The basics of licensing we have already reviewed in Section 3.1 of this deliverable and all the essential information about individual licensing can be deduced from there. In essence, CHIs, being licensees, have to negotiate the terms and conditions (i.e. contractual clauses; Table 1) with rightholders, being licensors, on an individual basis. Whereas they can heavily rely on the principle of contractual freedom, it is essential that the parties establish an agreement which is in line with applicable mandatory laws.

It is important to, however, add another essential remark: one has to differentiate between the licensing of a work and the sale/lease of a physical work. Selling/leasing the physical work itself does not necessarily entail the exclusive rights on the work. To obtain the necessary scope of exclusive/economic rights on the work, CHIs need to obtain authorization via a

¹⁰¹ See Pier Luigi Sacco, Guido Ferilli and Giorgio Tavano Blessi, ‘From Culture 1.0 to Culture 3.0: Three Socio-Technical Regimes of Social and Economic Value Creation through Culture, and Their Impact on European Cohesion Policies’ (2018) 10 Sustainability 3923.

¹⁰² Daniel Gervais, ‘Individual and Collective Management of Rights Online’ in Johan Axhamn (ed), *Copyright in a borderless online environment* (Norstedts Juridik 2012) 98.

¹⁰³ Danowsky and others (n 18) 99.

license with rightholders. Normally, rightholders can choose on whether they want to exercise their rights individually or collectively through a CMO (with such exceptions at the EU level¹⁰⁴).

Since CHIs in the EU cannot fully rely on exceptions and limitations to digitize and make the works available to the public (except for some specific cases), they need to enter into licensing agreements with the rightholders. However, the costs of individual licensing may be really high and burdensome for CHIs (see Figure 1). For these reasons, they normally opt for collective licensing.¹⁰⁵

3.3.2 Collective licenses

Background. Since 1700s collective management has been actively used by the artists working in theater companies in France. For instance, Victor Hugo and Honoré de Balzac established in the XIXth century the *Society of French Writers* aiming at collecting revenues from print publishers. Thereafter, some authors' societies started to emerge in different countries and soon they spread across the globe.

Collective management of rights was considered (and still is) an efficient manner of collecting royalties for the uses of the authors' works. However, with the international expansion of authors' societies, the need for international cooperation and harmonization became evident¹⁰⁶ and some international initiatives arose.¹⁰⁷ Since then, several countries fostered the creation of CMOs seeing them as a valuable mechanism for the licensing of works and for the enforcement of copyright. CMOs facilitate the methods of collecting and distributing royalties among the rightholders for the uses of the works and negotiate licensing agreements on their behalf. Over the years CMOs have also started serving other functions such as fighting against online piracy and getting involved in social and cultural matters.¹⁰⁸

Collective Management Organizations and their functioning. Relying on collective management can also be beneficial for the rightholders and the users. The use of collective management of rights give further negotiating powers to authors, especially when dealing with international companies or big organizations where the author is considered to be in a weaker bargaining position.

¹⁰⁴ See The Satellite and Cable Directive.

¹⁰⁵ Lucie Guibault and Simone Schroff, 'Extended Collective Licensing for the Use of Out-of-Commerce Works in Europe: A Matter of Legitimacy Vis-à-Vis Rights Holders' (2018) 49 IIC - International Review of Intellectual Property and Competition Law 916, 917.

¹⁰⁶ Daniel Gervais, *Collective Management of Copyright and Related Rights* (3rd ed., Alphen aan den Rijn : Kluwer law international 2016) 6.

¹⁰⁷ The International confederation of Societies of authors (CISAC) was created in 1926.

¹⁰⁸ Gervais (n 109) 7.

Collective management of rights is carried out by CMOs, which are considered to play an essential role in facilitating the dissemination of cultural content, especially in the digital environment. CMOs are seen as the main intermediaries between the rightholders and the users.¹⁰⁹

Collective management helps organizations such as cultural institutions that need to obtain multiple licenses for the uses of works in their collections. Given that CHIs are not normally the authors of the works, the use of collective management of rights instead of individual licensing significantly facilitates the clearance of rights (see Figure 1).

CMOs are defined by the CRM Directive as *'any organization which is authorized by law or by way of assignment, license or any other contractual arrangement to manage copyright or rights related to copyright on behalf of more than one rightholder, for the collective benefit of those rightholders, as its sole or main purpose, and which fulfils one or both of the following criteria: (i) it is owned or controlled by its members; (ii) it is organized on a not-for-profit basis'*.¹¹⁰

Often supported by governmental authorities, CMOs obtain from groups of rightholders - habitually categorized by sector i.e. publishing, visual arts - the *'ability to license on behalf of those rightholders'*.¹¹¹ Such capacity to operate on behalf of the rightholders is based on assignments of rights or on agency agreements where the rightholder allows the CMO to represent him.

Most CMOs operate within their boundaries of their territory - the country where the CMO is located - under the supervision of governmental authorities. This situation complicates the exercise of the rights clearance and has accelerated the need for multi-territorial licenses for the uses of works in the internet.¹¹² CMOs may nevertheless have the ability to operate in other territories through *'reciprocal representation agreements'* with other CMOs. In other words, once a CMO obtains the license to act on behalf of a number of rightholders, the CMO can enter into agreements with other CMOs with the objective of licensing each other's bundle of rights (from the rightholders). This *'pool'* of rights that CMOs manage is known as *'the repertoire'* of the CMO. CMOs may hence conclude non-exclusive agreements with other CMOs to exploit the rights that they represent in their respective territories.¹¹³

To protect the interests of rightholders, the CRM Directive establishes rules in the EU on the *'equal treatment and due diligence in respect to the distribution and payment of amount to the other CMOs'*.¹¹⁴ In addition, the principle of non-discrimination is created to protect those

¹⁰⁹ Guibault and Schroff (n 108) 917.

¹¹⁰ The CRM Directive Art.3(a).

¹¹¹ Gervais (n 109) 9.

¹¹² Lucie Guibault, *'Collective Rights Management Directive'* in Irini Stamatoudi and Paul Torremans (eds), *EU Copyright law: a commentary* (Edward Elgar Publishing 2014) 698.

¹¹³ Gervais (n 109) 158.

¹¹⁴ Gervais (n 109) 158.

rightholders that are not directly represented by a specific CMO equaling to those ones that are directly represented. Accordingly, CMOs cannot discriminate these rightholders and must apply the same tariffs, fees and conditions for the distribution and collection of revenues.

To facilitate the multi-territorial agreements, the international organization CISAC has several models of standard reciprocal agreements to facilitate the licensing of works.

Once a CMO has acquired as much repertoire from the rightholders as possible, the CMO will enter into licensing agreements with the users, e.g. CHIs. The price must be settled in these agreements and sometimes have a statutory origin as a mandatory compensation for rightholders. After receiving the economic compensation, the CMO will distribute the funds obtained among the represented rightholders.

Mandatory collective management. Mandatory collective management may be permitted only in specific cases regulated by law. We find some examples of mandatory collective management in the *acquis communautaire*. One of the cases is established in the Rental and Lending Directive which provides Member States the possibility to introduce an unwaivable right to remuneration.¹¹⁵ The Resale Right Directive¹¹⁶ and the SatCab Directive^{117,118} also include provisions on mandatory collective management.

The Collective Rights Management Directive (CRM). While collective licensing is traditionally rooted in the legal systems of Member States, a Directive on collective management¹¹⁹ was only adopted in 2014 even though the establishment of a legal harmonized framework for CMOs had been in the EU-policy pipeline for a long time.

The Infosoc Directive has already highlighted the need for ensuring transparency and rationalization of CMOs' operations, especially in the digital environment since¹²⁰ the existing national differences in regulating CMOs could provoke inefficiencies in the copyright and related rights management 'across the internal market and in detriment of rightholders and users'.¹²¹ In this context, the CRM Directive aimed at harmonizing the governance of CMOs within the EU Member States and at improving the functionality, transparency and accountancy of these organizations.¹²² The Directive also introduced rules for multi-territorial licensing for online rights of musical works which are not subject to this Study.

¹¹⁵ Rental and Lending Directive art.5.

¹¹⁶ Directive 2001/84/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 September 2001 on the resale right for the benefit of the author of an original work of art art.6(2).

¹¹⁷ See Art.9.1 of The Satellite and Cable Directive.

¹¹⁸ Gervais (n 109) 54.

¹¹⁹ The CRM Directive.

¹²⁰ Infosoc Directive Rec.17.

¹²¹ Guibault (n 115) 699.

¹²² Scollo Lavizzari and Viljoen (n 30) 87.

The rules in the Directive apply to all CMOs (see supra) that are established in the EU¹²³ regardless of their legal form or activity.¹²⁴¹²⁵

While we will not analyze all the provisions of the Directive in detail, there are certain **principles** that should be highlighted below as they govern the functioning of EU CMOs.

First, CMOs must act in the ‘best interest of the rightholders’ and should not establish any obligation on the rightholder that is not needed for the management of their rights.¹²⁶

Second, the rightholders have the freedom to choose the CMO that will represent them, as well as the rights and the types of works covered by the representation agreement and the right to terminate the agreements or to withdraw any right or works.¹²⁷ The freedom of creators is further emphasized in Article 5 which provides that rightholders have the possibility to grant licenses (on the side of the CMO) for non-commercial purposes. CHIs often engage in mass-digitization projects that could fall into this category. In this context, rightholders could, in principle, allow CHIs to undertake these activities regardless of the CMO.¹²⁸

Third, according to Article 6 of the Directive, a CMO shall accept any rightholder or any other entity representing the rightholders as long as they fulfill the established requirements¹²⁹.

Briefly, the Directive also establishes rules for the collection and distribution of revenues among the rightholders.¹³⁰ This provision is enshrined in the principles of non-discrimination and due-diligence of the CMOs in order to prevent abuses in the management of rights. Rules on collecting and distribution of revenues are ‘the cornerstone of an efficient collective management system’.¹³¹

Relationship between the CMOs and the users. Given that most of CHIs rely on collective management licensing systems, we should note that the CRM Directive also establishes certain rules in relation to the licensing between CMOs and users, e.g. CHIs. In this regard,

¹²³ The CRM Directive Art.2.

¹²⁴ Guibault (n 115) 715.

¹²⁵ The Directive also covers those ‘independent management entities, which are to be understood as an ‘organization which is authorized by law or by way of assignment, license or any other contractual arrangement to manage copyright or rights related to copyright on behalf of more than one rightholder, for the collective benefit of those rightholders, as its sole or main purpose, and which is: (i) neither owned nor controlled, directly or indirectly, wholly or in part, by rightholders; and (ii) organized on a for-profit basis’.

¹²⁶ The CRM Directive Art.4.

¹²⁷ This provision emanates from the Commission Decision on the *Daftpunk* case, where the European Commission established that the CMO could abuse its dominant position when introducing a mandatory clause according to which all the rights from a rightholder must be assigned without distinctions.

¹²⁸ Guibault and Schroff (n 108) 923.

¹²⁹ These membership requirements shall be based on transparent, objective and non-discriminatory criteria. If a rightholder is refused to be a member of the CMO it must be based on a reasoned decision.

¹³⁰ The CRM Directive Art.11-13.

¹³¹ Guibault (n 115) 740.

Article 16 obliges Member States to ensure that the negotiations between the CMOs and users are conducted in 'good faith'. However, CMOs often enjoy a higher bargaining position than users which is often the case for CHIs when entering in negotiations with CMOs for the digitization and dissemination of works within the CHIs collections.¹³² The second principle set by Article 16 of the CRM Directive concerns the licensing terms which 'shall be based on objective and non-discriminatory criteria'.¹³³

Finally, there are transparency rules in the Directive, especially in relation to the information that CMOs must provide to rightholders on the management of their rights, on other CMOs and users and on annual transparency reports.¹³⁴ Importantly, the information is provided to users 'on request from the user' basis.

The transparency obligations were criticized by some associations such as Communia at the beginning of the legislative process of the CRM Directive as they consider that obtaining information on the works of their collections is key for CHIs in order to 'develop a strategy for clearing rights'.¹³⁵ Communia (and other associations) also criticized the Directive for the lack of provisions that address the situations in which creators would want to provide their content through open access licenses as they could render incompatible with the provisions of the Directive¹³⁶. While they strongly advocated for such provisions during the legislative process, they were not included in the Directive.

3.3.2.1 *Extended collective licenses*

Particular attention should be given to the extended collective licensing ('ECL') system which is considered as one of the legal mechanisms that can help CHIs the most since it simplifies the clearance of rights, especially in relation to orphan works or OOWCs. This model, which originates in the 60s in the Nordic countries have been seen very positively in other countries around the world, including in the EU. This is the reason why the EU legislator opted for the introduction of the possibility to include ECL in the CDSM Directive.¹³⁷

One of the main features of the collective management by the CMOs is the possibility for them to issue 'blanket licenses' for a whole category of works and rightholders. This system significantly facilitates the clearance of rights of certain users, i.e. the CHIs. Yet, the repertoire may not be complete due to the fact that some rightholders do not want to enter into agreements with a certain CMO or the CMO does not have a bilateral agreement with a similar

¹³² Guibault (n 115) 750.

¹³³ The CRM Directive Art.16(2).

¹³⁴ The CRM Directive Art 18-22.

¹³⁵ COMMUNIA, 'Policy Paper on the Directive Proposal on Collective Management of Copyright' (2013) 3.

¹³⁶ COMMUNIA, 'Policy Paper #6: On the Proposed Directive on Collective Management of Copyright' (January 2013) <<https://www.communia-association.org/policy-papers/policy-paper-6-proposed-directive-collective-management-copyright/>>.

¹³⁷ CDSM Directive art.12.

CMO in another country as they may not exist in all countries.¹³⁸ In these cases, blanket licenses may be issued based on (i) a presumption, which accordingly, presumes the authorization of certain uses of works through a legal provision on the condition that the non-represented rightholders are not subject to a discriminatory treatment; and (ii) based on extended collective management.

The essence of the extended collective management is enshrined in the idea of the ‘sufficient representation’ of a CMO as a CMO generally represents a significant number of rightholders in a specific sector. In this case, the effects of a license are extended by law to those rightholders that are not represented by the CMO. Therefore, an ECL model could be generally defined as ‘a legal model whereby the binding effect of a collective agreement between an organization of copyright holders and a user of copyrightable works is extended to right holders who are not members of the organization’.¹³⁹

Even though ECL models have already been implemented in the Scandinavian countries within the EU,¹⁴⁰ the CDSM Directive introduced a number of provisions to facilitate the use of extended collective licenses. Since these provisions have been already assessed in detail in prior research, we will just mention here the most important features of the system. However, we should once again note that Member States are not obliged to transpose these provisions into their national laws, since those provisions are indicated as optional.

The use of ECL is highly dependent on the traditional legal systems of each country. This is the reason why Article 12 of the CDSM Directive offer different types of licensing regimes which countries could rely on when setting up the ECL model. In particular, the ECL can be conducted (i) through an extension of licensing agreements to rightholders that are not represented by that CMO; (ii) through a licensing agreement that is based in a legal mandate for those rightholders that are not represented by the CMO; and (iii) through a legal presumption of representation.

The Directive establishes that ECL should only apply in ‘well-defined areas of use’ and only when licensing with individual rightholders is ‘onerous and impractical to a degree that makes the required licensing transaction unlikely’.¹⁴¹ There are other two conditions that must be met in order to be able to use extended licenses. First, ECL are only applicable within their territory, and, second, CMOs issuing ECL will need to comply with the provisions of the CRM Directive (see supra).

Since ECLs represent rightholders that are not directly represented by the CMO, the Directive obliges Member States to introduce safeguards for the legitimate interests of rightholders. In

¹³⁸ Gervais (n 109) 66.

¹³⁹ Thomas Riis and Jens Schovsbo, ‘Extended Collective Licenses and the Nordic Experience - It’s a Hybrid but Is It a Volvo or a Lemon?’ (Social Science Research Network 2010) SSRN Scholarly Paper ID 1535230 1.

¹⁴⁰ See Deliverable 2.2 for an analysis of ECL model in Sweden.

¹⁴¹ CDSM Directive art 12(2).

particular, CMOs in the negotiated license agreements need to (i) be ‘sufficiently representative’ of rightholders for a specific type of work or other subject matter; (ii) guarantee equal treatment among rightholders, including in relation to the terms of the licence; (iii) provide an opt-out mechanism for rightholders who have not authorized the license to ensure that they can terminate the license at ‘any time easily and effectively’; (iv) take appropriate publicity measures to inform rightholders of the uses of their works before the use of such works has started.¹⁴²

ECL systems has been proven to be the most useful solution to address licensing problems for uses of digital cultural heritage.¹⁴³ It provides a flexible approach and sufficiently balances the interests of both rightholders and users. This balance is further achieved by negotiating agreements between the rightholders and the CHIs. ECL also provide CHIs with a legal mechanism for online (and even cross-border) uses of the in-copyright works held in their collections.

In essence, ECL is seen as one of the best solutions for CHIs. On the one hand, it allows rightholders to be remunerated for the uses of their works. On the other hand, through ECLs CHIs have a possibility to increase the access to their collections, thus, satisfying the public interest.¹⁴⁴

3.3.3 Open licenses

Unless CHIs are the rightholders of the works (which may happen in case of digital reproductions of works – see Section 3.4), CHIs have to enter into licensing agreements with the rightholders or with CMOs in order to use the in-copyright works in their collections unless they can rely on exceptions and limitations. Individual and collective licensing models have been explained in previous sections. In this section, we will provide a brief introduction to open licenses as a third licensing-in mechanism available to CHIs. Here, we should note that CHIs can make use of open licenses both for licensing-in and licensing-out purposes. However, since open licenses play a more significant role for licensing-out strategies of CHIs, open licensing will be analyzed in a more comprehensive manner in Section 3.4.

Background of open licenses. Open licensing is a relatively new licensing mechanism that has arisen as an outcome of the global ‘open movement’ in the last decades. In their essence, open licenses are specific types of licenses that incorporate licensing terms ensuring certain

¹⁴² CDSM Directive art 12(3).

¹⁴³ Danowsky and others (n 18) 97.

¹⁴⁴ See R Tryggvadottir, *European Libraries and the Internet: Copyright and Extended Collective Licences* (Mortsel : Intersentia 2018) 407; Johan Axhamn, ‘Cross-Border Extended Collective Licensing: A Solution to Online Dissemination of Europe’s Cultural Heritage?’ in Stefan Gradmann and others (eds), *Research and Advanced Technology for Digital Libraries*, vol 6966 (Springer Berlin Heidelberg 2011) <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-642-24469-8_59> accessed 13 February 2020; Riis and Schovsbo (n 142).

levels of ‘openness’. The open movement originated in the 50s in the field of software’s open source, which can be defined as ‘software that is freely available with its source code, to be used or altered by anybody as they wish. Commonly the only restriction is that it cannot be charged for, that its free distribution should not be hindered, and that the work of others should be properly respected’.¹⁴⁵

Open movements quickly expanded to other areas, for instance to open education (e.g. access to educational material and teaching resources); open access for scientific publications; open data and open science movements (data that can be used, modified and distributed by anyone (normally under an open license)); open government (which aims at claiming more transparency and accountability of the government as well as increasing social and citizens participation and engagement);¹⁴⁶ or open content and open licensing of, for instance, cultural content.

Here the ‘open content’ movement is of particular importance as it aims at providing the widest access and (re)use of cultural content as possible. This movement also sees the current copyright regime as one of the main obstacles to access to cultural content. Within the framework of this movement, open licenses are considered as enhancers of creativity and innovation since they develop a system which allows to (re-)use cultural content more efficiently.¹⁴⁷

Before moving on to the basics of open licenses, we should also briefly mention the OpenGLAM movement,¹⁴⁸ coordinated by the Open Knowledge Foundation. The OpenGlam aims at helping CHIs open up their collections and data to ensure that it can be freely used, modified and shared by anyone and for any purpose.¹⁴⁹ This aim is perceived as ‘free and open access to digital cultural heritage held by Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums’.

Definition of open licenses. While there is not any internationally agreed definition of an ‘open license’, open licenses are defined by the Open Knowledge Foundation as ‘licenses which grants permission to access, re-use and redistribute a work with few or no restrictions’.¹⁵⁰ This definition describes nine compulsory requirements that a license on a work *must* meet in order to be qualified as ‘open’. Such requirements are described in the table below:

¹⁴⁵ Hamilton and Saunderson (n 13) 9.

¹⁴⁶ See Hamilton and Saunderson (n 13) 14 ff.

¹⁴⁷ Angelopoulos and Guibault (n 2) 8.

¹⁴⁸ See more on ‘OpenGLAM. A Global Network on Sharing Cultural Heritage’ <<https://openglam.org/>>.

¹⁴⁹ Melissa Terras, ‘Opening Access to Collections: The Making and Using of Open Digitised Cultural Content’ (2015) 39 Online Information Review 733, 738.

¹⁵⁰ Open Knowledge Foundation, ‘Open Definition 2.1 Defining Open in Open Data, Open Content and Open Knowledge’ <<http://opendefinition.org/od/2.1/en/>>.

Core requirements¹⁵¹	Description
Use	<i>The license must allow free use of the licensed work</i>
Redistribution	<i>The license must allow redistribution of the licensed work, including sale, whether on its own or as part of a collection made from works from different sources.</i>
Modification.	<i>The license must allow the creation of derivatives of the licensed work and allow the distribution of such derivatives under the same terms of the original licensed work.</i>
Separation	<i>The license must allow any part of the work to be freely used, distributed, or modified separately from any other part of the work or from any collection of works in which it was originally distributed. All parties who receive any distribution of any part of a work within the terms of the original license should have the same rights as those that are granted in conjunction with the original work.</i>
Compilation	<i>The license must allow the licensed work to be distributed along with other distinct works without placing restrictions on these other works.</i>
Application to any purpose.	<i>The license must allow use, redistribution, modification, and compilation for any purpose. The license must not restrict anyone from making use of the work in a specific field of endeavor.</i>
Non-discrimination.	<i>The license must not discriminate against any person or group.</i>
Propagation.	<i>The rights attached to the work must apply to all to whom it is redistributed without the need to agree to any additional legal terms’.</i>
No charge.	<i>The license must not impose any fee arrangement, royalty, or other compensation or monetary remuneration as part of its conditions.</i>

Table 2: Core open licensing requirements

In addition to the requirements presented in the table, there are additional seven criteria that are ‘acceptable’ to include in a license and can still be considered as ‘open’. Among this criteria, we find the attribution requirement, e.g. to mention the authors of the work, or the ‘share-alike’ requirement which may require the redistribution of the work under the same license or same terms (see Section 3.4.1.2).

The Open Knowledge Foundation manages a list of ‘conformant’ licenses with the above-mentioned criteria which accordingly have to be ‘reusable, compatible and current in the sense that are widely used’.¹⁵² While there are other types of open licenses¹⁵³ that are not conformant with such criteria (including some CC licenses) the CC licenses are the most commonly used open licenses among the cultural heritage sector and governmental organizations (such as the European Commission). CC licenses will be explained in detail in Section 3.4.1.2.

Benefits of open licensing for licensing-in strategies of CHIs. Using open licenses for licensing-in purposes is highly beneficial for CHIs given that open licenses can be easily granted for any in-copyright work by any rightholder¹⁵⁴. Open licenses considerably simplify the licensing-in of cultural content as no agreement has to be actively negotiated between CHIs and

¹⁵¹ Open Knowledge Foundation, ‘Open Definition 2.1 Defining Open in Open Data, Open Content and Open Knowledge’ <<http://opendefinition.org/od/2.1/en/>>.

¹⁵² Open Knowledge Foundation, ‘Conformant Licenses’ <<https://opendefinition.org/licenses/>>.

¹⁵³ See Angelopoulos and Guibault (n 2) 53 ff.

¹⁵⁴ Hamilton and Saunderson (n 13) 54.

rightholders. Hence, CHIs can make use of open licenses that are granted by rightholders when digitizing their collections without entering into individual or collective license agreements with rightholders. However, it must be noted that the open content licensing does not mean that the works covered by such licenses are free of copyright or that users are given unlimited freedoms in respect to those works. On the contrary, open licenses provide standardised rights and information on the permitted uses of a work. A rightholder that grants open licenses may still be interested in protecting (at least some) of his exclusive rights¹⁵⁵ and thus CHIs must be aware of their obligations by using the work at stake.

¹⁵⁵ Angelopoulos and Guibault (n 2) 115 ff.

Figure 1: Advantages and disadvantages of licensing models

3.4 Licensing ‘out’ mechanisms for CHIs

In this section, we will focus on the mechanisms that CHIs can use when sharing and allowing re-use of digital copies of the works in their collections on their websites or third parties’ websites. Those mechanisms are generally covered by the term “licensing out” which mainly refers to the licenses that CHIs provide when making the digital copies of the works in their collections available to end-users. In addition, CHIs could make use of other mechanisms to state the status of protection (or lack of) underlying a work. These mechanisms, normally referred as ‘rights statements’ do not constitute a license but inform the end-user about the potential protection of the work not only in relation to copyright or related right but also in relation to their contractual or privacy provisions.

Allowing online access to the works in their collections and facilitating uses of them align with CHI’s responsibility to ensure the availability and dissemination of cultural heritage for the society as a whole. Hence, CHIs should actively engage with end-users to promote the use and re-use of the works in their collections.¹⁵⁶ However, providing online access to the works in their collections may entail certain problems for CHIs if the rights underlying those works are not clearly made known to end-users. For this reason, CHIs need to set up and follow an effective licensing out strategy when sharing the works in their collections on their websites or other platforms with end-users. CHIs should provide end-users with licenses or rights statements that they can rely on to, first, clearly communicate to their end-users the legal status of a shared work (e.g. whether it is copyright protected or in public domain) and, second, signal under which conditions the shared works can be (re-)used. Providing accurate and clear information for end-users is key if CHIs want to benefit from the opportunities offered by the DSM.

In order to share the works in their collections online, CHIs need to produce digital copies of those works, normally through scanning or photography. CHIs often have in their collections, in-copyright works as well as works in the public domain. In this context, we should take a closer look at two different scenarios:

- In the first scenario, the tangible work in the collection, of which a digital copy will be produced and shared, can be an in-copyright work. Here, we should note that producing digital copies of in-copyright works and providing online access to such copies constitute a copyright-infringing activity unless authorization of rightholders is secured (unless an exception or limitation applies). Hence, before producing digital copies of in-copyright works in their collections and providing online access to such copies, CHIs must enter into license agreements with rightholders. In this scenario, the possible further uses of the digital copies of those works would also be limited by the conditions of the initial license agreement concluded between CHIs and the

¹⁵⁶ Hamilton and Saunderson (n 13) 3.

rightholders. This also entails consequences for end-users with whom CHIs share those digital copies. For this reason, CHIs must clearly inform end-users about the rights and conditions that are covered by the license agreements that they conclude with rightholders of in-copyright works. This can be done by granting licenses to end-users or by providing end-users with rights statements.¹⁵⁷

- In the second scenario, the tangible work in the collection, of which a digital copy will be produced and shared, can be a work in the public domain. Here, the CHI has a higher degree of freedom in relation to that work as, in principle, it can be shared and re-used freely.

In both of the scenarios examined above, CHIs are in charge of the digitization of the work and the creation of digital copies. We observe in our previous research that CHIs can normally rely on the preservation exception at the EU level for the digital copies that they create for preservation purposes.¹⁵⁸ However the situation differs for making the digital reproductions of works available to the public. CHIs may be allowed to disseminate the digital copies of certain works on the internet (such as orphan works) and only for specific purposes if they can rely on exceptions and limitations. When there is no applicable exception, CHIs need to rely on licenses in case of in-copyright works.

The production of digital copies of works also entails legal consequences for both cases, namely for in-copyright works and works in the public domain. In particular, in case these copies of works are original enough to qualify for copyright protection, they can be protected by copyright. The digital copies of works can also be protected by other neighboring rights or may not be subject to exclusive protection.¹⁵⁹

In any case, for any digital copy of a work that the CHI is willing to share online, CHIs must provide a license or a right statement. The license or right statement must be clearly identified on the work, as well as any link to further information. Providing a clear strategy on licenses or declarations of works provide clear benefits for CHIs and for the reuse of works.¹⁶⁰

Particular attention to digital reproductions of works in the public domain. Since we have tackled this matter in depth in our previous research, we will just briefly mention below the main consequences for the access and re-use of cultural content.

¹⁵⁷ Hamilton and Saunderson (n 13) 81.

¹⁵⁸ See Deliverable 2.1 and 2.2. of the inDICES project.

¹⁵⁹ See Thomas Margoni, 'The Digitisation of Cultural Heritage: Originality, Derivative Works and (Non) Original Photographs' [2014] SSRN Electronic Journal <<http://www.ssrn.com/abstract=2573104>>; Frederik Truyen and Charlotte Waelde, 'Copyright, Cultural Heritage and Photography: A Gordian Knot?' in Karol Jan Borowiecki, Neil Forbes and Antonella Fresa (eds), *Cultural Heritage in a Changing World* (Springer International Publishing 2016) <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-319-29544-2_5> and Deliverables 2.1 and 2.2 of the inDICES project.

¹⁶⁰ Terras (n 152) 734.

D2.3 Public

Even though the doctrine generally agrees on the fact that digital reproductions of works in the public domain, that do not entail a great extent of human intervention and creativity, should not be subject to copyright or related rights protection,¹⁶¹ in some cases, CHIs will claim exclusive rights on the digital reproductions of public domain works in their collections.

Whether a digital reproduction of a work in the public domain is eligible for copyright protection mainly depends on the jurisdiction of the Member State where the digitization of that work takes place given that there is no harmonization of non-original photographs at the EU level. Under Article 6 of the Term Directive, Member States may provide that non-original photographs are subject to a neighboring right protection.¹⁶² As a result, a digital reproduction of a work in the public domain could be considered to be in the public domain in one jurisdiction (and therefore not protected by exclusive rights) while it could be granted certain rights in another. Therefore, the situation regarding the eligibility of these reproductions for exclusive rights protection is certainly unclear.

Some organizations such as Communia and Europeana, and the OpenGlam movement in general,¹⁶³ stress that works in the public domain should remain in the public domain in the digital environment. In consequence, no exclusive rights should be re-established in their technical reproductions¹⁶⁴ through copyright or related rights or any other IP. In addition, lawful copies of works in the public domain should be free for use, re-use and modification. According to Europeana, there is no legal basis to restrict the use of such works through technical or contractual measures.¹⁶⁵

This situation changes in relation to works of visual arts in the public domain since a limitation of the protection of digital reproductions of such works has been introduced by the Article 14 of the CDSM Directive, which accordingly, establishes that once the copyright of a work of visual arts has expired, it may be reproduced, communicated or used without the author's consent since it is in the public domain. In addition, no exclusive rights shall be attached to any copy of a public domain work of art, unless the reproduction constitutes its author's own intellectual creation.

Even when considering works that are in the public domain, moral rights may still prevail in the works depending on the jurisdiction where the CHI is located and, consequently, it may also limit their further uses.

In these situations, for instance, when a museum uploads a digital copy of a Leonardo Da Vinci work, copyright for which has already expired, in principle there should not be any

¹⁶¹ Margoni (n 162); Truyen and Waelde (n 162).

¹⁶² Directive 2011/77/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 September 2011 amending Directive 2006/116/EC on the term of protection of copyright and certain related rights 2011 art.6.

¹⁶³ See 'OpenGLAM. A Global Network on Sharing Cultural Heritage' (n 151).

¹⁶⁴ Europeana Foundation, 'The Europeana Public Domain Charter'.

¹⁶⁵ Europeana Foundation (n 167).

further restrictions for the free use of the work. Similarly, neither should there be any restrictions on the use of the surrogate of Da Vinci's work. Yet, the outcome will still depend on the 'originality' of the digital copy and on the applicable jurisdiction.

3.4.1 Granting licenses to end-users

To fulfill the objective of a wide dissemination of the collections, CHIs must have a clear licensing out strategy. As mentioned above, when the source work is protected by copyright or related right, CHIs must enter into a license agreement with the rightholder before providing online access to digital copies of that work. Accordingly, further uses of that work are determined by the rightholders' will. Further uses of the digital copy of that work may therefore be restricted by the licensing agreement that CHIs conclude with the rightholder. For instance, when a museum wants to make a digital copy of a painting available to the public, the exploitation of that digital copy of the painting by end-users may be subject to limitations (e.g. not to be used for commercial purposes) made by the painter (or the CMO on his behalf).¹⁶⁶

Yet, in a situation where the CHI uploads the digital copies of an in-copyright work of a third party on its website, the CHI must specify under which license the digital copy is made available to the public. The crucial aspect for CHIs when sharing digital copies of works under a license is to provide enough information on the terms of the license to end-users. For instance, CHIs must indicate the uses of that digital copy (e.g. permitted non-commercial uses, such as educational or research activities) permitted under the license agreement.

In this scenario, CHIs can choose to grant licenses to end-users in order to facilitate the further (re-)uses of the shared digital copies of the works. However, CHIs can grant licenses for digital copies of the in-copyright works in their collections only when they obtained an authorization from rightholders permitting such (re-)use. They can nevertheless grant licenses for the digital copies of works in the public domain that are granted copyright (when they are original enough to merit copyright protection) or a related right protection (if applicable).

3.4.1.1 *Open licensing for licensing-out strategies of CHIs*

Although CHIs can grant different types of licenses for the digital copies that they share with end-users, granting open licenses to end-users entails particular benefits for both CHIs and end-users. For CHIs, open licenses certainly simplify entering into multiple agreements as they can be granted as non-exclusive standardized licenses to users which determine the permitted uses of a work. From the user's perspective, these licenses are schematic and easy to understand.

¹⁶⁶ Hamilton and Saunderson (n 13) 73.

End-users that are willing to modify or remix a particular digital copy can do so as long as such activities comply with the terms of the license that they were granted (or when they can rely on an exception or limitation). Open content licenses also impose some obligations upon the end-users. For instance, if a user wants to modify a digital copy of a work under a Share Alike (SA) or a non-commercial (NC) CC-license, this person must use the work for non-profit purposes, e.g. research or private study. If the user wants to disseminate it further, the work must be circulated under the same license or terms and will always have to mention the author of the pre-existing work. The use of open licenses still creates rights and obligations for the end-users which shows that open licensing does not constitute a 'virtual public domain'.¹⁶⁷

Providing a wider open access to increasing audiences and offering the re-use of the CHIs' collections would result in high benefits for all the parties involved, including rightholders and end-users (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Benefits of open licenses

- First, CHIs could benefit from having a **stronger impact** by lowering the barriers before the re-use of their cultural content. This is clearly exemplified by Wikipedia or other related projects. Having stronger impact is not only beneficial for users but also for the cultural institutions as their material can be quicker and easier accessed.
- Second, open licensing increase the **availability of works**, even of those works that museums or archives may hold in a 'second row'. Normally institutions cannot show all their collections due to the lack of space. Providing access to them through open licenses could facilitate the sharing and potential re-use of such works.

¹⁶⁷ Angelopoulos and Guibault (n 2) 135.

- Third, in relation to the availability of works, providing open licenses to their materials **boosts creativity and innovation**. Access to a wider variety of material has been proven to enhance the creativity among society. There is a vast amount of cultural heritage and knowledge that can be re-used.
- Fourth, the licensing mechanism is clearly simplified by the use of standard open licenses. Opting for **simplicity** in licensing agreements is translated into lower transaction costs.¹⁶⁸

Another argument that is used to ‘force’ CHIs to make use of open licensing systems relates to the ‘public investment’. Most of these institutions do receive public funding for the preservation, study and promotion of their collections and therefore they should maximize the public benefit. Opening access to their collections, engaging in research projects or offering their expertise to organizations and communities are only some examples of how openness could benefit the society as a whole.¹⁶⁹

Open access would, thus, promote a free of charge access to the images of their collections while fostering the reuse of their works. Some CHIs, cultural organizations and policy makers have strongly advocated for an ‘opening’ of the collections and spoke against the appropriation of digital reproductions of works in the public domain.

The potential downsides of open licensing for CHIs:

- Open licensing models could clash with the generation of revenues through digital business models, mainly by licensing digital reproductions of works in their collections since CHIs often aim at returning the economic investment made in the digitization of their collections by charging reuse license fees for the use of their images.¹⁷⁰ The utilization of open access models could be seen as **a threat to these business models**, especially for more commercial-oriented institutions or photographic associations.¹⁷¹
- Open licenses may result in the **loss of control** on the re-use of the works. Providing the works in open terms may generate certain fear to some CHIs since once the work is uploaded on the internet, it is available to be re-used. Thus, they will not be able to control how a certain image is modified.

¹⁶⁸ Hamilton and Saunderson (n 13) 74 ff.

¹⁶⁹ Hamilton and Saunderson (n 13) 70.

¹⁷⁰ Hamilton and Saunderson (n 13) 74.

¹⁷¹ Andrea Wallace and Ellen Euler, ‘Revisiting Access to Cultural Heritage in the Public Domain: EU and International Developments’ (2020) 51 IIC - International Review of Intellectual Property and Competition Law 823, 848.

3.4.1.2 CC licenses

The most popular and extensively used types of open licenses that are granted by CHIs for licensing-out purposes are the CC licenses. The non-profit organization Creative Commons was founded in 2001 with the objective of increasing the number of works that could be disseminated, accessed, (re-)used and redistributed in a legal manner. It was evident at the time that rightholders often did not know which rights they possessed and in which manner they wanted to share their works.

The new licensing system would allow rightholders to easily identify how they wanted to share their works and which rights they wished to retain.¹⁷²

CC licenses can be defined as ‘standardized agreements between a rights holder and any possible user, on the basis of which the user acquires the right to access the work without being charged for royalties and to use it according to the license grant’.¹⁷³ Consequently, these licenses offer a standard and simple mechanism according to which the author can make the works available free of charge. These licenses are subject only to a limited range of restrictions. Rightholders have the possibility to choose among a combination of various permissions and conditions that will govern the work depending on the degree of ‘openness’ they wish to implement.

Works under a CC license can be used according to the terms agreed in the license. For the works under copyright, there are six standard licenses apart from the Public Domain Mark and the CC0 Dedication. Through these licenses, the rightholder can choose to what extent the work can be re-used. With the objective of facilitating the dissemination and re-use of cultural content for both the rightholder and the user, CC licenses put in place different ‘features’ that the author can combine as he wishes.¹⁷⁴

- **Attribution (BY):** All the CC licenses (except from the CC0 which is actually not a license, see below) require to attribute the work properly to the author. The attribution requirement under CC licenses is considered as a ‘low barrier’ before the reuse of cultural content at the same time since it complies with the moral right of attribution,¹⁷⁵ which is of special relevance for CHIs. Under this feature, the user agrees to keep all the copyright notices and to always give attribution to the author(s).¹⁷⁶

¹⁷² Hamilton and Saunderson (n 13) 14.

¹⁷³ Angelopoulos and Guibault (n 2) 206.

¹⁷⁴ See the different combined options on Creative Commons, ‘About CC Licenses’ <<https://creativecommons.org/about/ccllicenses/>>.

¹⁷⁵ Hamilton and Saunderson (n 13) 55.

¹⁷⁶ Angelopoulos and Guibault (n 2) 207.

- **Share Alike (SA):** the author can also set the requirement that the new work must be circulated under the same conditions, the same or similar licensing terms. This feature originated from the principles of open content (see supra) and consequently, it would be unfair if a user is allowed to use a work under a CC license and then he restricts further uses. We may however draw attention to the fact that this feature challenges the re-use of digital material based on other kind licenses which may be incompatible.¹⁷⁷
- **Non-commercial (NC):** making use of this feature allows the author to restrict the use of the work to non-commercial purposes. The use of such module in a CC license makes the reuse of cultural content easier for non-commercial purposes as often rightholders often have commercial interests on the uses of their works. The use of the non-commercial feature in a CC license is really interesting for educational or research purposes which do not aim at generating profit.
- **No Derivatives (ND):** the author can restrict the possibilities of the user to distribute the work that has been modified or remixed. According to Hamilton and Saunderson, this type of licenses are the least frequently used.¹⁷⁸

The Zero (CC0) dedication is not a license *per se*. It should be understood as a mechanism that waives all the copyright existing in a particular work. Moral rights, as far as possible and depending on the jurisdiction, may also be waived under this tool and this is the reason why it is considered as the most liberal option to share content. However, the use of this mechanism may entail some risks as it would be difficult to enforce in jurisdictions where moral rights prevail indefinitely. When an author shares the content under the CC0 dedication, the work can be accessed, used and reused by anyone and for any purpose. The CC0 dedication only applies to in-copyright works and should not be confused with other tools used to clarify the status of works that are not protected by copyright i.e. works in the public domain.

Further, Creative Commons created the **Public Domain Mark**, which is a 'label' for works that have already been identified as free of copyright. Yet, in some jurisdictions these works may still be subject to moral rights i.e. in those jurisdictions where moral rights are perpetual (see below). CHIs are encouraged to use the public domain mark to identify those works that are in the public domain.

Finally, the fact that a work is under a CC license does not mean that it is free of any other IPRs such as trademark or any other contractual terms, as it only deals with copyright.

¹⁷⁷ Hamilton and Saunderson (n 13) 55.

¹⁷⁸ Hamilton and Saunderson (n 13) 56.

3.4.2 Mechanisms facilitating the rights information to end-users

In addition to granting licenses to end-users, CHIs can also make use of other mechanisms to help end-users identify the permitted uses in relation to a particular work. In Section 3.4.1.2, we described two mechanisms under the management of Creative Commons, namely, the CC0 Dedication and the Public Domain Mark. These mechanisms are very effective in communicating the copyright status of a work to end-users.

The **CC0 Dedication** is a ‘tool’ that waives all the copyright existing in a particular work. This dedication is widely used by the cultural institutions in relation to the digital reproductions of works that are in the public domain. Most of the museums and libraries that have made their collections in the public domain available to the public waive all their exclusive rights for the benefit of end-users by applying a CC0 Dedication. For instance, the Smithsonian Museum¹⁷⁹ released 2.8 millions of digital copies in open content terms¹⁸⁰ or at the EU level, the Rijksmuseum¹⁸¹ or the Paris Musées¹⁸² share digital copies of the works in the public domain under the CC0 Dedication.

The **Public Domain Mark** was also created by Creative Commons and constitutes a tool for those works that have already been identified as free of copyright. Yet, in some countries moral rights that are linked to those works may still remain. These works can in principle be used, modified and reproduced freely without restrictions. The National Gallery of Denmark (SMK) was one of the first institutions to release digital copies of works in the public domain under open content terms by using the Public Domain Mark. When making those digital copies available to the public, the National Gallery released the following statement: ‘the images have been handed over to the Public Domain using the Creative Commons Public Domain dedication to clearly signify that they are no longer subject to copyright. They belong to the public – ‘to you’.¹⁸³

In addition, other organizations such as Europeana are promoting the use of other mechanisms to identify copyright or related rights or any other restriction on the works contained in CHIs collections. It is worth highlighting here the ‘**rights statements**’¹⁸⁴ initiative which is managed by a consortia of organizations, including the European Foundation. This initiative provides 12 standardized rights statements for online cultural content.

¹⁷⁹ See Smithsonian, ‘Smithsonian Terms of Use’ <<https://www.si.edu/termsofuse>>.

¹⁸⁰ Victoria Heath, ‘Smithsonian Releases 2.8 Million Images + Data into the Public Domain Using CC0’ (27 February 2020) <<https://creativecommons.org/2020/02/27/smithsonian-releases-2-8-million-images-data-into-the-public-domain-using-cc0/>>.

¹⁸¹ ‘Rijksmuseum Open Data Policy’ <<https://www.rijksmuseum.nl/en/research/conduct-research/data/policy>>.

¹⁸² ‘Paris Musées. Les Images Libre de Droits’ <<https://www.parismuseescollections.paris.fr/fr>>.

¹⁸³ SMK, ‘Free Download of Images. Art in the Public Domain’ <<https://www.smk.dk/en/article/free-download-of-images/>>.

¹⁸⁴ Rights Statements, <<https://rightsstatements.org/page/1.0/?language=en>>

There are three main categories of rights statements (see the categorization below) which aim at covering all the possible situations for which the use of a work may be restricted, in particular copyright restrictions and permitted uses, including the identification as an EU orphan work and contractual or other legal-related restrictions such as, for instance, the implication of traditional cultural expressions. The last category relates to the impossibility of identify the accurate status of the copyright on a particular work.¹⁸⁵

- In Copyright: Statements for works that are in copyright.
 - In copyright
 - In copyright – EU orphan work
 - In copyright- educational use permitted
 - In copyright – non-commercial use permitted
 - In copyright – rightholders unlocatable or unidentifiable.
- No copyright: Statements for works that are not in copyright.
 - No copyright – contractual restrictions
 - No copyright – non-commercial use only
 - No copyright – other known legal restrictions
 - No copyright – Unites States
- Other: Statements for works where the copyright status is unclear.
 - Copyright not evaluated
 - Copyright undetermined
 - No known copyright

Importantly, a **lack of uniform practices** has been identified when labelling the works under CHIs collections which may confuse the audience. A standardization of the websites of cultural institutions has been acknowledged as a best practice that facilitates the activities for end-users and that could further contribute to the reuse of images.¹⁸⁶

3.4.3 Alternative mechanisms for facilitating user's information

DRM technologies is a term that refers to a wide variety of technologies and that is placed under the broader term of technical protection measures ('TPMs' as seen in Section 3.2.1). In general, these technologies are used by rightholders to identify, track and control the uses of their works. While these technologies may restrict the access to works (some of these technologies have already been explained in Section 3.2.1), they may also offer opportunities for rightholders and CHIs to better identify and manage the uses of a work.¹⁸⁷ In this section, we will briefly refer to the rights data that may underly a work or a digital copy of a work

¹⁸⁵ See further information on the 'Rights Statements' <<https://rightsstatements.org/page/1.0/?language=en>>.

¹⁸⁶ Foteini Valeonti, Melissa Terras and Andrew Hudson-Smith, 'How Open Is OpenGLAM? Identifying Barriers to Commercial and Non-Commercial Reuse of Digitised Art Images' (2019) 76 *Journal of documentation* 1, 21.

¹⁸⁷ Rina Elster Pantalony, *Managing Intellectual Property for Museums: Guide* (2013 ed, WIPO 2013) 30.

which provides information to the end-user on the rightholder, the scope of the license and the permitted uses.

DRM systems have the capacity to include detailed information on a particular work and can facilitate the dissemination of works by developing identification methods. An efficient DRM system can also include particular considerations about the terms of a license¹⁸⁸ facilitating the tracking for CHIs. However, the traditional modes of rights information can be easily removed and altered. For this reason, blockchain technologies are receiving an increased interest in the creative industries.

Particular attention to blockchain technologies. Blockchain technologies¹⁸⁹ are one of the latest new technologies that are supposedly provoke a fundamental change in the organization of our relations and institutions.¹⁹⁰ It is expected to be widely utilized in asset management and government services in general.¹⁹¹

The safety and value of these new modes of operations have developed their use in other domains and could actually play a role in the field of copyright. For instance, the use of blockchain technologies in the copyright field could address certain inefficiencies and problems cause by a centralized system, i.e. based on decisions of CMOs.¹⁹²

Nowadays blockchain technologies can also include a software that can be executed in its own by interacting with the stored data and acting in an autonomous manner. These blockchain technologies are also referred to as ‘smart contracts’. The smart contracts could facilitate copyright transactions based on the terms of a license.

While this technology has been deployed in some domains, such as the online music sector, some CHIs have already started using this technology. For the time being uses of blockchain technologies of cultural content could be restricted to two main activities. First, a big amount of accurate data of cultural works could be stored through ‘blockchain’ registries (a passive approach). This data could be consulted by anyone and could be updated and surveilled by CMOs. Second, blockchain technologies could be used to facilitate transactions with the rightholders by contributing to the licensing of works or by tracking the uses of such works.

¹⁸⁸ Raman Mittal, ‘Mechanisms to Make End-Users of Copyrighted Works Pay Through Levy and DRM’ 115, 131.

¹⁸⁹ Blockchain technologies can be defined as ‘a distributed ledger, or an append only database, of which every user has a continuously updated authoritative copy. Anyone who has access to the ledger has access to the same full transaction history and the ability to verify the validity of all records. Sophisticated consensus mechanisms ensure that new entries can only be added to this distributed database if they are consistent with earlier records. This distributed database has the capacity to record any kinds of data’ (Bodo, Gervais and Quintais).

¹⁹⁰ Balazs Bodo, Daniel Gervais and João Quintais, ‘Blockchain and Smart Contracts: The Missing Link in Copyright Licensing?’ (2018) 26 International journal of law and information technology 311, 311.

¹⁹¹ Jake Goldenfein and Dan Hunter, ‘Blockchains, Orphan Works, and the Public Domain’ (2017) 41 The Columbia journal of law & the arts 1, 42.

¹⁹² Goldenfein and Hunter (n 194) 10.

(an active approach) This interactive approach may ease the enforcement of copyright in the digital environment.¹⁹³

One of the applications of blockchains in the cultural heritage sector has been put forward by Goldenfein and Hunter in relation to the orphan works. The authors suggest the use of an artificial intelligence system to perform the diligent searches required under the Orphan Works Directive before being declared orphan. In a second step the system would introduce this registry of searches in a blockchain technology.¹⁹⁴ They do not suggest to create a 'new registry' but to automatize the search for orphan works and place the works into the 'orphanage'. Once they are declared orphans, the blockchain technology could go one step further by allowing 'automatic licensing' of orphan works. In the EU, this may not be necessary for CHIs given the exception created under the Orphan Works Directive.

According to the authors, this system could also be extended to other types of works such as OOCWs and works in the public domain. The use of blockchain technologies could be seen as a 'solution' to the use of public domain works as this registry could communicate a 'public license to use' as the authors call it, or signal the status of a work in the public domain.¹⁹⁵

Yet, while this technology looks promising in the field of copyright law, there are still some challenges to implement it. In order to combine blockchains with licensing systems, significant coordination efforts from the rightholders/licensors and the licensees are required. In addition, most of the entities developing these technologies aim at generating profits which contrast with the public missions of CHIs. Thus, the implementation of these technologies in

¹⁹³ Bodo, Gervais and Quintais (n 193) 324.

¹⁹⁴ Goldenfein and Hunter (n 194).

¹⁹⁵ Goldenfein and Hunter (n 194) 24.

the cultural heritage sector may be delayed due to the fact that this industry is mostly driven by the public interest and does not seek the generation of revenues.

Figure 1: Licensing 'in' and 'out' for CHIs

3.5 Conclusion

As shown in our previous research, many CHIs are working towards the goal of raising awareness of their collections. They aim at providing wide access to the works in their collections and promote their reuse. Yet, we observe how CHIs still struggle with making their works available to the public in the digital environment mainly due to the complexities of the copyright regime and the multiple licenses CHIs need to establish with the rightholders. We can draw the following conclusions and suggest preliminary recommendations in an attempt to facilitate the work of CHIs towards sharing their collections online:

- *Licensing strategy.* For this reason a clear licensing strategy integrated in the CHI's policies would certainly facilitate the further uses of works. Ideally, CHIs should obtain as many rights as possible during the license negotiation processes with rightholders. In particular, obtaining the right of communication to the public from the rightholder, and more specifically, the right of making works available in the digital environment would help provide access to such works. However, obtaining broader scope of rights from rightholders is often difficult for CHIs mainly due to the fact that negotiating individual licensing with each rightholder is extremely costly and burdensome. In addition, while collective licensing is the best option for clearing a vast amount of rights and works, CHIs are normally not in a strong position to negotiate with CMOs.
- *Use of ECL and licenses for OOCWs.* The introduction of two new licensing systems within the CDSM Directive looks highly promising for CHIs. The new licensing mechanism for OOCWs will certainly facilitate the uses of such works, which have a high value for research or educational purposes. The use of ECL, if implemented by the Member States, can also contribute to ease the 'clearance of rights' by significantly simplifying the issuance of licenses for each category of works (as long as it is implemented and subject to some conditions). We therefore would recommend policy and law makers to make the most use of such possibilities and work together with CHIs and CMOs on the arrangement of new licenses.
- *Clear information to users when licensing out.* Furthermore, in order to provide a wider availability of works for the general public it is of vital importance that CHIs offer clear underlying information on the licenses and rights statements related to a particular work. Recent studies¹⁹⁶ have shown the positive effects of setting up clear digital strategies, as well as installing mechanisms that provide accurate information to end-users on the 'status' of works in CHIs collections, including the permitted scope

¹⁹⁶ See for instance Elizabeth Joan Kelly, 'Digital Cultural Heritage and Wikimedia Commons Licenses: Copyright or Copywrong?' (2019) 3 Journal of copyright in education and librarianship 1; Valeonti, Terras and Hudson-Smith (n 189).

of (re-)uses. For instance, it is important to clearly state the status of digital reproductions of works in the public domain. Providing information on works in the public domain aligns with the public-interest missions of CHIs and encourages the re-use of their collections.

- *Standardization of rights information.* Cultural institutions need to provide clear information on the licenses and rights statements of the works in their collections in a similar and accessible manner. This can be done by clearly indicating the works that can be ‘freely’ used without restrictions and those that are protected by copyright or subject to other related limitations.¹⁹⁷ The different practices in relation to the information of works used among institutions or even inside the same institution may generate confusion for end-users.

¹⁹⁷ Valeonti, Terras and Hudson-Smith (n 189) 20.

4 References

Angelopoulos C and Guibault L, *Open Content Licensing : From Theory to Practice*, vol 48419 (Amsterdam: Amsterdam University Press 2011)

Axhamn J, 'Cross-Border Extended Collective Licensing: A Solution to Online Dissemination of Europe's Cultural Heritage?' in Stefan Gradmann and others (eds), *Research and Advanced Technology for Digital Libraries*, vol 6966 (Springer Berlin Heidelberg 2011) <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-642-24469-8_59> accessed 13 February 2020

Bently L and Sherman B, *Intellectual Property Law* (4th ed., Oxford : Oxford university press 2014)

Bodo B, Gervais D and Quintais J, 'Blockchain and Smart Contracts: The Missing Link in Copyright Licensing?' (2018) 26 *International journal of law and information technology* 311

COMMUNIA, 'Policy Paper on the Directive Proposal on Collective Management of Copyright' (2013)

—, 'Policy Paper #6: On the Proposed Directive on Collective Management of Copyright' (January 2013) <<https://www.communia-association.org/policy-papers/policy-paper-6-proposed-directive-collective-management-copyright/>>

Creative Commons, 'About CC Licenses' <<https://creativecommons.org/about/cclicenses/>>

Danowsky P and others, *Copyright in a Borderless Online Environment* (Stockholm : Norstedts Juridik 2012)

de la Durantaye K, 'Finding a Home for Orphans: Google Book Search and Orphan Works Law in the United States and Europe' (2011) 21 *Fordham Intellectual Property, Media & Entertainment Law Journal* 229

Dusollier S, 'Scoping Study on Copyright and Related Rights and the Public Domain' (Social Science Research Network 2011) SSRN Scholarly Paper ID 2135208 <<https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=2135208>> accessed 23 March 2020

Elster Pantalony R, *Managing Intellectual Property for Museums: Guide* (2013 ed, WIPO 2013)

European Commission, 'Factual Summary Report on the Open Public Consultation on Digital for Cultural Heritage' (2020)

European Union Intellectual Property Office, 'Orphan Works Database' <<https://euipo.europa.eu/ohimportal/en/web/observatory/orphan-works-db>>

Europeana Foundation, 'The Europeana Public Domain Charter'

Geiger C, Frosio G and Bulayenko O, 'Facilitating Wider Access to Europe's Cultural Heritage in the Digital Environment: Opinion of the CEIPI on the European Commission's Copyright

Reform Proposal, with a Focus on Access to Out-of-Commerce Works' (Social Science Research Network 2018) SSRN Scholarly Paper ID 3287734 <<https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=3287734>>

Gervais D, 'Individual and Collective Management of Rights Online' in Johan Axhamn (ed), *Copyright in a borderless online environment* (Norstedts Juridik 2012)

—, *Collective Management of Copyright and Related Rights* (3rd ed., Alphen aan den Rijn : Kluwer law international 2016)

Giulia Priora, 'Copyright Law and the Promotion of Scientific Networks: Some Reflections on the Rules on Co-Authorship in the EU' (2019) 9 Queen Mary Journal of Intellectual Property 217

Goldenfein J and Hunter D, 'Blockchains, Orphan Works, and the Public Domain' (2017) 41 The Columbia journal of law & the arts 1

Guibault L, 'Evaluating Directive 2001/29/EC in the Light of the Digital Public Domain' in Melanie Dulong de Rosnay and Juan Carlos De Martin (eds), *The Digital Public Domain*, vol 2 (1st edn, Open Book Publishers 2012)

—, 'Collective Rights Management Directive' in Irini Stamatoudi and Paul Torremans (eds), *EU Copyright law: a commentary* (Edward Elgar Publishing 2014)

Guibault L and Canat J-F, 'WIPO Study on Exceptions and Limitations in Museums.Pdf'

Guibault L and Schroff S, 'Extended Collective Licensing for the Use of Out-of-Commerce Works in Europe: A Matter of Legitimacy Vis-à-Vis Rights Holders' (2018) 49 IIC - International Review of Intellectual Property and Competition Law 916

Hamilton G and Saunderson F, *Open Licensing for Cultural Heritage* (London : Facet Publishing 2017)

Hansen DR and others, 'Solving the Orphan Works Problem for the United States' (2013) 37 The Columbia Journal of Law & the Arts 55

Heath V, 'Smithsonian Releases 2.8 Million Images + Data into the Public Domain Using CC0' (27 February 2020) <<https://creativecommons.org/2020/02/27/smithsonian-releases-2-8-million-images-data-into-the-public-domain-using-cc0/>>

Janssens M-C and Michaux B, 'Intellectual Property Rights: Copyright and Trademark Issues' in Laurent Garzaniti and others (eds), *Electronic Communications, Audiovisual Services and the Internet. EU Competition Law & Regulation*. (Sweet & Maxwell; London 2020)

Janssens M-C and Tryggvadottir R, 'Facilitating Access to Orphan and Out of Commerce Works to Make Europe's Cultural Resources Available to the Broader Public' [2014] SSRN Electronic Journal <<http://www.ssrn.com/abstract=2538097>>

Jordan M, *Putting Content Online: A Practical Guide for Libraries* (Oxford : Chandos, 2006)

Keller P, 'Explainer: What Will the DSM Directive Change for Cultural Heritage Institutions?' [2019] *Europeana Foundation* 9

Kelly EJ, 'Digital Cultural Heritage and Wikimedia Commons Licenses: Copyright or Copywrong?' (2019) 3 *Journal of copyright in education and librarianship* 1

Kerremans R, 'A Critical View on the European Draft Directive for Orphan Works' (2012) 2 *Queen Mary Journal of Intellectual Property* 38

Margoni T, 'The Digitisation of Cultural Heritage: Originality, Derivative Works and (Non) Original Photographs' [2014] *SSRN Electronic Journal* <<http://www.ssrn.com/abstract=2573104>>

Mittal R, 'Mechanisms to Make End-Users of Copyrighted Works Pay Through Levy and DRM' 115

Open Glam, 'Copyright Clearance and Labeling Works: A Primer: A Webinar with Annabelle Shaw, Melissa Levine and Victoria Stobo.' (August 2020) <<https://medium.com/open-glam/copyright-clearance-and-labeling-works-a-primer-ab40d0992582>>

Open Knowledge Foundation, 'Conformant Licenses' <<https://opendefinition.org/licenses/>>

—, 'Open Definition 2.1 Defining Open in Open Data, Open Content and Open Knowledge' <<http://opendefinition.org/od/2.1/en/>>

'OpenGLAM. A Global Network on Sharing Cultural Heritage' <<https://openglam.org/>>

'Paris Musées. Les Images Libre de Droits' <<https://www.parismuseescollections.paris.fr/fr>>

Pier Luigi Sacco, Guido Ferilli and Giorgio Tavano Blessi, 'From Culture 1.0 to Culture 3.0: Three Socio-Technical Regimes of Social and Economic Value Creation through Culture, and Their Impact on European Cohesion Policies' (2018) 10 *Sustainability* 3923

Rajan MTS, *Moral Rights: Principles, Practice and New Technology* (Oxford University Press 2011) <<https://www.oxfordscholarship.com/10.1093/acprof:osobl/9780195390315.001.0001/acprof-9780195390315>>

'Rights Statements' <<https://rightsstatements.org/page/1.0/?language=en>>

Riis T and Schovsbo J, 'Extended Collective Licenses and the Nordic Experience - It's a Hybrid but Is It a Volvo or a Lemon?' (Social Science Research Network 2010) *SSRN Scholarly Paper* ID 1535230

'Rijksmuseum Open Data Policy' <<https://www.rijksmuseum.nl/en/research/conduct-research/data/policy>>

Scollo Lavizzari C and Viljoen R, *Cross-Border Copyright Licensing: Law and Practice* (Cheltenham : Edward Elgar Publishing 2018)

Senftleben M, 'Institutionalized Algorithmic Enforcement – The Pros and Cons of the EU Approach to UGC Platform Liability' (Social Science Research Network 2020) SSRN Scholarly Paper ID 3565175 <<https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=3565175>> accessed 24 April 2020

Smithsonian, 'Smithsonian Terms of Use' <<https://www.si.edu/termsfuse>>

SMK, 'Free Download of Images. Art in the Public Domain' <<https://www.smk.dk/en/article/free-download-of-images/>>

Sterling JAL, *Sterling on World Copyright Law* (4th ed., London : Sweet & Maxwell 2015)

Stobo V and others, 'Current Best Practices among Cultural Heritage Institutions When Dealing with Copyright Orphan Works and Analysis of Crowdsourcing Options' (2018) <<http://diligentsearch.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/05/EnDOW-Report-3.pdf>>

Terras M, 'Opening Access to Collections: The Making and Using of Open Digitised Cultural Content' (2015) 39 Online Information Review 733

Travkina E, Sacco P and Morari B, 'Culture Shock: COVID-19 and the Cultural and Creative Sectors' (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) 2020)

Truyen F and Waelde C, 'Copyright, Cultural Heritage and Photography: A Gordian Knot?' in Karol Jan Borowiecki, Neil Forbes and Antonella Fresa (eds), *Cultural Heritage in a Changing World* (Springer International Publishing 2016) <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-319-29544-2_5>

Tryggvadottir R, *European Libraries and the Internet: Copyright and Extended Collective Licences* (Mortsel : Intersentia 2018)

Valeonti F, Terras M and Hudson-Smith A, 'How Open Is OpenGLAM? Identifying Barriers to Commercial and Non-Commercial Reuse of Digitised Art Images' (2019) 76 Journal of documentation 1

Vézina B, 'Creative Commons. We're Against Digital Rights Management. Here's Why.' (4 December 2020) <<https://creativecommons.org/2020/12/04/were-against-digital-rights-management-heres-why/>>

Wallace A and Euler E, 'Revisiting Access to Cultural Heritage in the Public Domain: EU and International Developments' (2020) 51 IIC - International Review of Intellectual Property and Competition Law 823

Weber RH and Chrobak L, 'Legal Implications of Digital Heritagization' [2016] RESET. Recherches en sciences sociales sur Internet <<http://journals.openedition.org/reset/826>>

Case-law

Falco Privatstiftung and Thomas Rabitsch v Gisela Weller-Lindhorst (C-533/07) EU:C:2009:257

Hewlett-Packard Belgium SPRL v Reprobel SCRL (C-572/13) EU:C:2015:750

Martin Luksan v Petrus van der Let (C-277/10) EU:C:2012:65

Legal and policy acts

Commission Recommendation 2006/585/EC of 24 August 2006 on the digitisation and online accessibility of cultural material and digital preservation (2006) OJ L 236

Communication from the European Commission 'A Single Market for Intellectual Property Rights Boosting creativity and innovation to provide economic growth, high quality jobs and first class products and services in Europe' COM(2011) 287 final 2011

Communication from the European Commission on copyright in the knowledge economy COM(2009) 532 final 2019

Council Directive 93/83/EEC of 27 September 1993 on the coordination of certain rules concerning copyright and rights related to copyright applicable to satellite broadcasting and cable retransmission

Directive 96/9/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 March 1996 on the legal protection of databases

Directive 2001/29/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 May 2001 on the harmonisation of certain aspects of copyright and related rights in the information society

Directive 2001/84/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 September 2001 on the resale right for the benefit of the author of an original work of art

Directive 2004/48/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 April 2004 on the enforcement of intellectual property rights

Directive 2006/115/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2006 on rental right and lending right and on certain rights related to copyright in the field of intellectual property

Directive 2009/24/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 April 2009 on the legal protection of computer programs

Directive 2011/77/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 September 2011 amending Directive 2006/116/EC on the term of protection of copyright and certain related rights 2011

Directive 2012/28/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 on certain permitted uses of orphan works (2012) OJ L299/5

Directive 2014/26/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 February 2014 on collective management of copyright and related rights and multi-territorial licensing of rights in musical works for online use in the internal market

Directive (EU) 2019/790 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on copyright and related rights in the Digital Single Market and amending Directives 96/9/EC and 2001/29/EC 2019

European Commission, Memorandum of Understanding: Key Principles on the Digitisation and Making Available of Out-of-Commerce Works (2011)

Regulation (EC) No 593/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 June 2008 on the law applicable to contractual obligations (Rome I)

Regulation (EC) No 864/2007 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 July 2007 on the law applicable to non-contractual obligations (Rome II)

Regulation (EU) No 1215/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2012 on jurisdiction and the recognition and enforcement of judgments in civil and commercial matters

Table of figures & tables

Table 1: Licensing clauses: an overview from the perspective of CHIs as licensees	14
Table 2: Core open licensing requirements	33
Figure 1: Advantages and disadvantages of licensing models.....	36
Figure 2: Benefits of open licenses	41
Figure 3: Licensing 'in' and 'out' for CHIs.....	49

5 Annex I. Summary of inDICEs second consultation workshop

A (second) consultation workshop was organized by the inDICEs partners on the 20 and 21st of April 2021. The workshop was split into two sessions. The first session centered around *'Emergent forms of digital cultural production/re-production, participation and re-use of CHI contents in DSM'* and was organized by WP1 partners whilst the second session was organized within the framework of the WP2 on the topic *'Sharing collections sustainably and meaningfully: A brief introduction to rights management in cultural organisations'*.

Various external stakeholders, mainly CHI representatives, were invited to give their presentations on licensing mechanisms as well as were invited to elaborate upon the manner in which their respective cultural institutions share their collections online, focusing on sharing their best practices on open content and open licenses.

After a short introduction of the inDICEs project and the research carried out within WP2, Ryan King, the representative of the Smithsonian Open Access Initiative, gave a keynote speech on *'Facilitating content reuse: A boost for online engagement and reach of the CHIs'*. He elaborated upon the open access policies applied within the Smithsonian institutions and the challenges they face within the institution, especially with relation to data interoperability and lack of data and information on the collections.

The keynote speech was followed by two presentations from EU cultural institutions. The first presentation was made by Saskia Scheltjens (the Rijksmuseum) on *'Sustainability of open access models'*.¹⁹⁸ After sharing with the audience the manner in which the open access models were used in this institutions, she highlighted the need of inviting the audience to interact with the collections of the museum. Karin Glassemann (the Swedish National Museums) was in charge of the second presentation that revolved around *'Tools to indicate the reuse possibilities of digital cultural heritage'*. In her presentation, she noted the importance of not only attracting audience to the museum but also to keep them connected with their collections regardless the actual place they access them from. This session was followed by a Q&A debate with the audience moderated by Kristina Petrasova (the Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision and inDICEs partner).

The second part of the workshop started with a presentation of Maarten Zeinstra on *'Making a public domain determination'* where he explained the challenges of dealing with digital reproductions of works in the public domain and shared certain tips with the audience. Annabelle Shaw (the British Film Institute) continued the workshop by giving a presentation on *'Relying on licenses and exceptions'*. Interestingly, she mentioned the difficulties of relying on exceptions and limitations for all the activities that they would like to carry out. Thus, they

¹⁹⁸ The Rijksmuseum open access initiative has been introduced 10 years ago.

were forced to entering into licensing agreements, which led to further legal certainty. She also shared best practices on the risk assessments of providing access to in-copyright works. However, she emphasized that in practice it was not possible to take actions related to the sharing of digital reproductions by cultural institutions that would be completely free of legal risk. The last speech was given by Jerker Ryden (the National Library of Sweden) on '*The use of Extended Collective Licensing*'. He elaborate upon the ECL model active used in Sweden and stated that using such type of licences facilitated the rights clearance for the library while reducing the risk of facing individual claims from rightholders. The workshop continued with a Q&A session moderated by Konrad Gliściński (Centrum Cyfrowe and inDICEs partner).

The **key insights** from this workshop can be summarized as follows:

- Open access models for CHIs are only possible in relation to a digitization strategy as they entail certain challenges on data access, data interoperability, etc. Yet, they offer high benefits for both users and CHIs since they permit further interaction within the users and their collections.
- While the challenges of providing access to digital reproductions of works in the public domain remain, the CDSM Directive may clarify the situation and make a statement of the need of liberating the public domain works.
- Given the divergences in the implementation of exceptions and limitations and their narrow scope, relying on exceptions and limitations does not always entail the legal certainty that CHIs need. Their activities must be supplemented by licenses with rightholders or CMOs on their behalf. ECL are considered as a good solution for the provision of online access to cultural heritage.

CHIs are increasingly engaging in the use of risk assessments for the uses of in-copyright works in their collections. However, it is not possible to take actions related to the providing access to digital reproductions by cultural institutions that would be completely free of legal risks. An open question is whether CHIs, as institutions with a public mission, should be burdened with such risks.